

Final Report for Period: 04/2007 - 03/2008

Submitted on: 07/09/2008

Principal Investigator: Warnick, Wendy K.

Award ID: 0101279

Organization: Arctic Research

Submitted By:

Warnick, Wendy - Principal Investigator

Title:

Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program

Project Participants

Senior Personnel

Name: Warnick, Wendy

Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes

Contribution to Project:

Name: Wiggins, Helen

Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes

Contribution to Project:

Director of Programs, directs and supervises program and project activities undertaken through this agreement.

Post-doc

Graduate Student

Undergraduate Student

Name: Grabinska-Marusek, Kalina

Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes

Contribution to Project:

Student Assistant

Name: Jenkins, Philip

Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes

Contribution to Project:

Web Technician

Name: Polly, Joshua

Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes

Contribution to Project:

Videographer

Technician, Programmer

Name: Behr, Sarah

Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes

Contribution to Project:

Project Manager

Name: Buxbaum, Tina

Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes

Contribution to Project:

Project Manager

Name: Coen, Ross
Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes
Contribution to Project:
 Project Manager

Name: Druckenmiller, Matthew
Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes
Contribution to Project:
 Project Manager

Name: Ferguson, Daniel
Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes
Contribution to Project:
 Project Manager

Name: Horn-Hanssen, Birte
Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes
Contribution to Project:
 Project Manager

Name: Klauder, Joseph
Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes
Contribution to Project:
 Project Manager

Name: Loring, Alysa
Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes
Contribution to Project:
 Project Coordinator

Name: Mitchell, Susan
Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes
Contribution to Project:
 Project Manager

Name: Owens, Ronnie
Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes
Contribution to Project:
 Web developer, programmer

Name: Polly, Bryce
Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes
Contribution to Project:
 System Administrator

Name: Shnorro, Reija
Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes
Contribution to Project:
 Project Manager

Name: Slater, Laura
Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes
Contribution to Project:
 Project Manager

Name: Thomas, Ryan
Worked for more than 160 Hours: Yes

Contribution to Project:

Project Manager

Name: Topkok, C. Sean**Worked for more than 160 Hours:** Yes**Contribution to Project:**

Indigenous Curriculum Specialist

Name: Wade, Ben**Worked for more than 160 Hours:** Yes**Contribution to Project:**

Web Developer

Name: Want, Matthew**Worked for more than 160 Hours:** Yes**Contribution to Project:**

Project Manager

Name: Warburton, Janet**Worked for more than 160 Hours:** Yes**Contribution to Project:**

Project Manager

Name: York, Alison**Worked for more than 160 Hours:** Yes**Contribution to Project:**

Project Manager

Other Participant**Research Experience for Undergraduates****Organizational Partners**

University of Alaska Fairbanks Campus

Columbia University Lamont Doherty Earth Observatory

University of California-Santa Barbara

University of Arizona

U.S. Army Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory

Other Collaborators or Contacts

ARCUS has had many other collaborators and contacts over the past seven years. A list is included as an appendix in the attached narrative report.

Activities and Findings**Research and Education Activities:**

With support from this agreement, ARCUS has served the goals of the NSF Arctic Sciences programs by nurturing the growth and development of arctic research and education through tasks that cannot be accomplished as effectively by individual researchers, institutions, agencies, or by currently existing advisory bodies. ARCUS supports the efforts of the NSF and the research community by coordinating planning, disseminating information, and creating a focal point for new opportunities in arctic science and education.

In cooperation with the arctic science community, ARCUS provided organizational support to the U.S. arctic science programs through work in four major categories:

1. Arctic Community Science Planning- Coordinating science planning for the arctic research community at several levels, including activities for: Arctic Research Support and Logistics, Geographic Information Systems, the Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH), the Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST), and Data Coordination and Management activities;
2. Arctic Sciences Section Coordination- Organizational support for research programs included in the NSF Office of Polar Programs Division of Arctic Sciences (formerly Arctic Sciences Section), including the Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program and the Arctic Social Sciences Program (ASSP), as well as development of information and outreach materials for the Arctic Section as a whole.
3. Arctic Science Education- Development, implementation, and coordination of arctic science educational programs and activities, including: Arctic Science Education Activities, Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series, Arctic Science Education Report, Arctic Alive!, and Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating (TREC); and
4. Information and Outreach- Activities to disseminate information about arctic research to the scientific community, policy and decision-makers, and to the public, including: Witness the Arctic newsletter, Website and Internet Resources, ArcticInfo Listserve, the Directory of Arctic Researchers, the Internet Media Archive, and other community outreach and education activities.

Additional detailed information about research and education activities is included in a PDF attached to this report.

Findings:

ARCUS has facilitated scientific planning for arctic research efforts by working with the scientific community through workshops, surveys, Internet communications, and other means to define science priorities and research initiatives. ARCUS has organized dozens of meetings and published numerous scientific planning documents that reflect the recommendations of the arctic research community on scientific priorities in various research fields. All of the activities described in this report supported community science planning processes for the NSF Arctic Sciences Division and provided information and support for the conduct of arctic research and education and, therefore, contributed to the overall excellence and advancement of arctic research and education supported by the National Science Foundation. Since 2001, significant progress has been made on the following major NSF priorities in arctic research:

- the development and implementation of an Arctic Observing Network, recommended by the ARCUS Research Support and Logistics working group, guided by the scientific perspective of the interagency Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH), and cooperating with international partners;

- the development and implementation of new research opportunities in the Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program focusing on synthesis and thematic questions; and
- the development and implementation of an integrated ecosystem study of the Bering Sea (BEST), funded through a special research partnership with the North Pacific Research Board; the study includes a significant social science and community research component.

Additional detailed information about project results is included in a PDF attached to this report.

Training and Development:

Details on specific science education projects implemented by ARCUS, which include the Visiting Speakers' Series and Teachers and Researchers - Exploring and Collaborating (TREC), can be found in the attached report. All ARCUS activities strive to:

- Ensure that high-quality information and education in arctic science is available to the general public, students, teachers, and Natives of the Arctic.
- Enable interested and talented students to pursue scientific careers in the Arctic.
- Ensure that the scientific and technical workforce exists to meet the challenges of the arctic research agenda.

In addition, all ARCUS science planning activities such as workshops and e-Meetings seek to involve young investigators and support their professional development. Major ARCUS meetings (SEARCH Open Science Meeting, ARCSS All-Hands Meeting, Arctic Forum) include a student travel scholarship program; we increasingly include sessions specifically designed to promote mentoring relations with more senior scientists and to enable young investigators to contribute their perspectives to meeting reports. Several of the leaders in our current science planning efforts are young female investigators (Maribeth Murray, Andi Lloyd, Katie Walter, Allison Gaylord).

Outreach Activities:

ARCUS has used a variety of information and outreach methods to disseminate timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, and the public. These methods include a newsletter, the ARCUS website, email listserves, online directories and archives, and several other projects. In addition, ARCUS, which is based in Alaska, makes a special effort to inform and involve members of the Alaska Native community.

Additional detailed information about information and outreach activities is included in the attached report.

Journal Publications

Books or Other One-time Publications

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, "Arctic Observation Integration: Workshops Report", (2008). , Published Bibliography: Fairbanks, Alaska. 55 pages

HARC Science Steering Committee, Arctic Research Consortium of the United

States, "Designing the Human Dimension into an Arctic Observing Network", (2007). Brochure, Published
Bibliography: Fairbanks, Alaska. 2 pages

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, "Surface Transformations in the Arctic Environment (STATE): Implementation Plan", (2007). Science Plan, Published
Bibliography: Fairbanks, Alaska. 33 pages

Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH), "Study of Environmental Arctic Change: Plans for Implementation During the International Polar Year and Beyond. Report of the SEARCH Implementation Workshop, May 23 - 25, 2005.", (2005). Workshop Report, Published
Bibliography: Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 90 pages.

Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH), "Proceedings of the SEARCH Open Science Meeting, 27-30 October 2003, Seattle, Washington", (2005). Workshop Report, Published
Bibliography: Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 370 pages.

BEST Science Steering Committee, "Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) Implementation Plan", (2005). Science Plan, Published
Bibliography: Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 39 pages

BEST Science Steering Committee, "Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) Science Plan", (2004). Science Plan, Published
Bibliography: Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 82 pages.

Arctic GIS Working Group, "Arctic Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) for Scientific Research - White Paper", (2004). White Paper, Published
Bibliography: Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 41 pages

Working Group, "Guidelines for Improved Cooperation between Arctic Researchers and Northern Communities", (2004). , Published
Bibliography: Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 20 pages.

ARCSS Science Steering Committee, "Proceedings of the Arctic System Science Program All-Hands Workshop 2002", (2002). Workshop Proceedings, Published

Bibliography: Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 271 pages

Schlosser, P., W. Tucker, W. Warnick, and A. York, "Arctic Research Support and Logistics: Strategies and Recommendations for System-scale Studies in a Changing Environment", (2003). Science Plan, Published
Bibliography: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. Fairbanks, Alaska. 95 pages

Various, "The Earth is Faster Now: Indigenous Observations of Arctic Environmental Change", (2002). Book, Published
Editor(s): Krupnik, Igor, and Jolly, Dyanna
Collection: The Earth is Faster Now: Indigenous Observations of Arctic Environmental Change
Bibliography: Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 384 pages. ISBN 0-9720449-0-6.

Arctic Science Education Working Group, "Arctic Science Education: Recommendations from the Working Group on Arctic Science Education to the National Science Foundation", (2002). Workshop Report, Published
Bibliography: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. Fairbanks, Alaska. 56 pages

Vörösmarty, C.J., L.D. Hinzman, B.J. Peterson, D.H. Bromwich, L.C. Hamilton, J. Morison, V.E. Romanovsky, M. Sturm, and R.S. Webb, "The Hydrologic Cycle and its Role in Arctic and Global Environmental Change: A Rationale and Strategy for Synthesis Study", (2001). Science Plan, Published
Bibliography: Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 84 pages.

, "NSF-ARCSS Workshop on Arctic System Hydrology: Meeting White Papers", (2001). White Papers, Published
Editor(s): Hinzman, L. and C. Vörösmarty
Collection: NSF-ARCSS Workshop on Arctic System Hydrology: Meeting White Papers
Bibliography: Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 86 pages

Taagholt, J., and J. C. Hansen, "Greenland: Security Perspectives", (2001). Book, Published
Editor(s): Transl. Daniel Lufkin
Bibliography: Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 94 pages

Various, "Abstracts from the Arctic Forum, 2001-2007", (2007). Proceedings, Published
 Editor(s): ARCUS
 Collection: Abstracts from the Arctic Forum, 2001-2007
 Bibliography: 7 Volumes. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic
 Research Consortium of the United
 States. Various pages

Various, "Witness the Arctic: Chronicles of the NSF Arctic Sciences Program, 2001-2007", (2007). Newsletter, Published
 Editor(s): Warnick, W., S. Behr, R. Coen, S. Mitchell, and A. York
 Bibliography: 8 Issues. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States.
 Various pages.

Web/Internet Site

URL(s):

<http://www.arcus.org>

Description:

The Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS) website houses numerous pages dedicated to the facilitation, coordination, and implementation of arctic science. It offers a variety of resources, ranging from programmatic pages to databases. The various linked pages achieve ARCUS' purpose of acting as a synthesizer and disseminator of scientific information. Several key resources housed within the ARCUS website are outlined below.

ALIAS

http://www.arcus.org/Logistics/about_alias.html

ALIAS is searchable database of for 40 research stations and sites and 47 vessels involved in arctic research; information included ownership and management, capabilities, scientific equipment and space, communications and data equipment, scheduling, and other information.

ARCSS

<http://www.arcus.org/arcss/>

The ARCSS website details the NSF Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program, research efforts, funding opportunities, synthesis efforts, community planning and surveys, meetings and workshops, ARCSS publications, and other related resources.

Arctic Alive!

<http://www.arcus.org/ArcticAlive/index.html>

Arctic Alive! is a distance-learning environment for learners to be transported virtually to unique and remote locations within the arctic region. Arctic Alive! is not an information Internet site but an interactive, real-time, and unique web-based education program. It uses a variety of delivery methods and e-learning strategies to deliver arctic research to the classroom.

Arctic Calendar

<http://calendar.arcus.org/>

The Arctic Calendar is a searchable calendar of events jointly maintained by ARCUS, the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC), and the Arctic Ocean Sciences Board (ASOB). The calendar is intended to assist anyone who is interested in identifying relevant Arctic events and conferences and to help organizers avoid conflicting meeting dates. Information may be submitted to the calendar by anyone organizing arctic events.

ArcticInfo Archive

<http://www.arcus.org/arcticinfo/index.html>

The ArcticInfo archive is a searchable online archive of all the messages posted to ArcticInfo, a moderated, broadcast only email list that provides arctic researchers with timely information about funding opportunities, important events, publications, position announcements, and other useful news.

Arctic Visiting Speakers

http://www.arcus.org/arctic_speaker/index.html

This website provides useful information about the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series and offers a link to the Speaker's Bureau- an online directory of arctic researchers and experts who are available to visit organizations, communities or schools to give presentations.

BEST

<http://www.arcus.org/Bering/index.html>

This section of the website supports the Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) planning process, and includes information on previous and upcoming meetings. The page gives users access to downloads of reports and background materials, and provides links to other organizations with interests in the Bering Sea.

Directory of Arctic Researchers

<http://www.arcus.org/researcher/index.html>

The Directory of Arctic Researchers is a searchable online database of records intended to aid links among individual investigators, institutions, funding agencies, and arctic stakeholders, thereby facilitating arctic research and education efforts. Directory entries include complete contact information, science specialties, current arctic research interests, and information about specific projects, areas of expertise, and collaborations.

Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC)

<http://www.arcus.org/harc/index.html>

The HARC website provides background information on projects, publications, meetings and workshops, and useful links and contacts to support the development of Arctic-relevant human dimensions research.

Internet Media Archive

<http://media.arcus.org/>

The ARCUS Internet Media Archive (IMA) is a searchable archive of photos, graphics, videos, and presentations that have been collected for various purposes and shared through the Internet. The contents of this archive are organized by the photographer, contributor, or presenter's name, by event, by organization, and by keywords. Each item in the collection is accompanied by information about the content, the contributor or source, and usage or access requirements.

Press Site

<http://www.arcus.org/press/index.html>

The Arctic in the News press page provides users with links to press briefings and related materials when relevant Arctic science appears in the news.

SEARCH Website

<http://www.arcus.org/search/index.php>

The SEARCH website provides a comprehensive and up-to-date resource for information on: SEARCH science and projects, meetings and activities, coordination structure and membership, related national and international programs, and other timely information for SEARCH scientists, agency personnel, and the public.

SEARCH Project Catalog

<http://www.arcus.org/search/catalog/public/catalogsearch.php>

The SEARCH Project Catalog is an online database-driven catalog of SEARCH-relevant

projects launched to track and communicate SEARCH-funded and SEARCH-related research projects, initiatives, and programs. The online project database contains information on: project personnel, project abstract, funding agencies, keywords, regions and locations studied, SEARCH activity areas, weblinks to data, and other relevant information. The database interface allows users to browse, search, and submit project information. There are currently 69 projects in the Project Catalog, which is under continual development and improvement as additional projects and user functionality is added.

TREC

<http://www.arcus.org/TREC/index.php>

The TREC webpage provides comprehensive information on the Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating program. It includes information on previous expeditions, educational resources, and related links, including a link to the related program, PolarTREC.

Other Specific Products

Contributions

Contributions within Discipline:

Contributions to Other Disciplines:

As outlined elsewhere, including in the attached detailed report, ARCUS activities in every category are designed to use the guidance from the disciplinarily diverse arctic research and education communities to support the logical growth of effective research, education, and outreach programs. ARCUS

- performs tasks that cannot be accomplished as efficiently by individual researchers, institutions, agencies, disciplinary groups, or by currently existing advisory bodies, and
- provides tools and resources that enable these entities to share and coordinate their information and efforts.

Contributions to Human Resource Development:

In addition to specific programs providing opportunities in arctic science and education, ARCUS has integrated numerous approaches that promote human resource development into planning coordination and information dissemination activities.

ARCUS implemented three science education programs, which provide opportunities for research and teaching in arctic science-Arctic Alive!, Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating (TREC) and PolarTREC (which expanded on TREC and includes both poles). All of these programs improve teacher content knowledge and instructional practices by providing research opportunities to teachers and connect teachers and researchers to better convey real-world polar science to classroom environments-human resource development occurs for the teachers and the researchers that participate.

ARCUS uses numerous information and outreach approaches to disseminate timely information about arctic science research and teaching opportunities to broad audiences, which include not only the arctic science community but also a large number of young investigators, students, and members of the public. These methods, which include a newsletter, the ARCUS website, and email listservers, also provide audiences with a

centralized source of relevant arctic science information, information to which many individuals/groups may not otherwise have access. Online directories and archives promote networking between these same audiences. In addition, ARCUS, which is based in Alaska, makes a special effort to inform and involve members of the Alaska Native community.

ARCUS continually strives to promote broad community involvement when conducting science planning activities for programs such as SEARCH and ARCSS, including the involvement of minority participants and other under-represented groups. ARCUS actively seeks to involve young investigators in workshops and e-Meetings to support their professional development. Major ARCUS meetings (SEARCH Open Science Meeting, ARCSS All-Hands Meeting, Arctic Forum) include a student travel scholarship program; we increasingly include sessions specifically designed to promote mentoring relations with more senior scientists and to enable young investigators to contribute their perspectives to meeting reports.

Contributions to Resources for Research and Education:

ARCUS is the organization that represents the U.S. arctic research community. ARCUS has contributed substantially to the literature in arctic science and education community planning, maintains a website that is a major information hub for the arctic science community, and provides information tools such as e-Meetings for community use.

Contributions Beyond Science and Engineering:

Increasingly, ARCUS programs, project activities, meetings, and workshops include discussions of the relevance of arctic research to issues of public welfare, including:

- consideration of impacts of environmental change on ecosystems and societies, both in the Arctic and globally;
- the role of the research community in public literacy.

Many of these discussions have resulted in the development of recommendations and implementation of suggested strategies in a variety of formats and venues.

Categories for which nothing is reported:

Any Journal

Any Product

Contributions: To Any within Discipline

**Arctic
Research
Consortium
of the
United States**

Member Institutions:

University of Alaska Anchorage
University of Alaska Fairbanks
University of Alaska Statewide
Alaska North Slope Borough
Dept. of Wildlife Management
Arctic Centre
University of Lapland
Arizona State University
Bates College
Center for Northern Studies
University of Colorado
University of Delaware
Dartmouth College
Desert Research Institute
Embry-Riddle
Aeronautical University
Foundation for Glacier
and Environmental Research
Idaho State University
Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory
of Columbia University
Louisiana State University
University of Manitoba
Marine Biological Laboratory
University of Massachusetts Amherst
University of Miami
University of New Hampshire
Northern Illinois University
Ohio State University
Oregon State University
San Diego State University
Sandia National Laboratories
Scandinavian Seminar
Smithsonian Institution
SRI International
Texas A&M University
University of Washington
Woods Hole
Oceanographic Institution
Woods Hole Research Center

**3535 College Road
Suite 101
Fairbanks, Alaska 99709
USA
907.474.1600
Fax: 907.474.1604
E-mail: info@arcus.org
<http://www.arcus.org>**

9 July 2008

Renée Crain
Office of Polar Programs, Room 755
National Science Foundation
4201 Wilson Blvd.
Arlington, VA 22230

Dear Ms. Crain:

Attached is the Final Report of the Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS) as required in Section F-1 of Cooperative Agreement ARC-0101279, between the National Science Foundation and ARCUS. The narrative description of activities and accomplishments and the attached financial reports are for the period 1 April 2001 through 31 March 2008.

Included in the annual report, as specified in the Cooperative Agreement, are:

- a brief summary outlining the major activities and accomplishments;
- a narrative summary of accomplishments with discussion of major changes in direction or pace, by individual project activity;
- a one-page, multi-column table summarizing the entire seven-year cooperative agreement by Form 1030 categories and showing the budget and actual expenditures from 1 April 2001 through 31 March 2008;
- a one-page summary showing costs through March 2008 by five major tasks: arctic community science planning, NSF Arctic Sciences Section coordination, arctic science education, information and outreach, and core support;
- a five-page, multi-column table, organized by individual project activity, showing the approved seven-year budget, the actual expenditures through March 2008, and the remaining funds or shortfall in each line item.

The attached final report reflects the growing activity in broad-based, systematic and integrative approaches to arctic science. The ARCUS board of directors and staff are pleased at the achievements of the past seven years and the work accomplished on behalf of the arctic research community and NSF through this cooperative agreement. We are pleased to be continuing our work with NSF and the arctic research community on these important initiatives under a new five-year cooperative agreement. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me.

Sincerely,

Wendy K. Warnick
Executive Director

THE ARCTIC RESEARCH CONSORTIUM OF THE UNITED STATES

Final Report

1 April 2001–31 March 2008
Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279

The narrative describes activity for the period 1 April 2001 through 31 March 2008, the entire period of Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279. The total award for this period was \$13,053,541. The active period of this agreement, originally established from 1 April 2001 to 31 March 2006, was extended several times through a series of supplementary awards and no-cost extensions while the proposal for a new five-year agreement, submitted in January 2006, underwent review and award processing. These supplements and extensions to the five-year award were as follows:

- Supplemental funding: 31 March 2006–31 August 2006: \$1,188,044
- No-cost extension: 1 September 2006–31 December 2006
- No-cost extension: 1 January 2007–31 March 2007
- Supplemental funding: 1 April 2007–30 June 2007: \$633,392
- Supplemental funding: 1 July 2007–30 September 2007: \$816,200
- No-cost extension: 1 October 2007–31 December 2007
- Supplemental funding: 1 January 2008–31 March 2008: \$747,267

This protracted use of short-term funding instruments from 2006–2008 significantly increased the administrative burden on ARCUS and made project planning and budgeting difficult; nevertheless, the overall pace and scope of activities was maintained throughout the period.

With support from this agreement, ARCUS has served the goals of the NSF Arctic Sciences Division programs by nurturing the growth and development of arctic research and education through tasks that cannot be accomplished as effectively by individual researchers, institutions, agencies, or by currently existing advisory bodies. ARCUS supports the efforts of the NSF and the research community by coordinating planning, disseminating information, and creating a focal point for new opportunities in arctic science and education.

In cooperation with the arctic science community, ARCUS provided organizational support to the U.S. arctic science programs through work in four major categories:

1. **Arctic Community Science Planning**—Coordinating science planning for the arctic research community at several levels, including activities for: Arctic Research Support and Logistics, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), the Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH), the Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST), and Data Coordination and Management activities;
2. **Arctic Sciences Section Coordination**—Organizational support for research programs included in the NSF Office of Polar Programs Division of Arctic Sciences (formerly Arctic Sciences Section), including the Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program and the Arctic Social Sciences Program (ASSP), as well as development of information and outreach materials for the Arctic Section as a whole;
3. **Arctic Science Education**—Development, implementation, and coordination of arctic science educational programs and activities, including: Arctic Science Education Activities, Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series, Arctic Science Education Report, Arctic Alive!, and Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating (TREC); and

4. Information and Outreach—Activities to disseminate information about arctic research to the scientific community, policy and decision-makers, and to the public, including: *Witness the Arctic* newsletter, Website and Internet Resources, ArcticInfo Listserve, the Directory of Arctic Researchers, the Internet Media Archive, and other community outreach and education activities.

An additional 5th category is the provision of core support for ARCUS' NSF-funded activities—dedicated funding of the costs incurred by program activities that simultaneously support multiple Cooperative Agreement projects.

In all its activities, ARCUS seeks to advance arctic science by increasing and engaging collaborative participation of all interested groups and individuals, fostering interdisciplinary exchanges, and making effective use of available resources.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.1 Arctic Research Support and Logistics

Building on activities funded under Cooperative Agreement OPP-9727899 from 1998–2001, ARCUS worked with the 10-member Research Support and Working Group (RSLWG), co-chaired by Peter Schlosser of Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory and Terry Tucker of the Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory, to develop a new report updating the priorities from the 1997 report *Logistics Recommendations for an Improved U.S. Arctic Research Capability*. The updated report provided guidance for investments in physical infrastructure and other resources to benefit the arctic research community in the coming decade. With the increasingly urgent need to monitor changes in the arctic environment, the report recommended an expansion of support to enable research that entails large-scale, long-term observational components and system-scale synthesis and modeling activities, including organizing and connecting a distributed pan-arctic observing network. Intended for use by all federal agencies with interests in the Arctic, the report is a “living document” that will require future updates as research priorities change and logistics assets improve. Specific activities included:

Working Group Communications—Planned and convened meetings of the working group: (1) in December 2001 in conjunction with the American Geophysical Union (AGU) Fall Meeting to discuss and revise the first draft of the report; (2) in September 2002 in conjunction with the AAAS Arctic Science Conference to develop information and additional material for key gaps in report content; and (3) by teleconference 7 times between 2001 and 2003. Met with RSLWG co-chairs in person and by teleconference 15 times between 2001 and 2003 to discuss progress and identify needed contributions. Developed, updated, and maintained a webpage to support working group communications and document review and revision (<http://www.arcus.org/Logistics/index.html>).

Report Drafting, Community Review, and Development of Final Report—With oversight by the working group, circulated draft materials for review, collected review comments, solicited additional materials, and coordinated response to reviews: (1) by the working group in December 2001 and January 2002; (2) by the working group and selected individuals in March 2003 and August 2003; (3) by open community review in May 2003; 29 individuals commented. Following the community review, an additional 35 people were asked to provide specific material for the report, including VECO Polar Resources and NSF staff. Worked with the RSLWG to incorporate comments from community review and finalize the report.

Publication and Distribution—Printed 2000 copies of the final report, *Arctic Research Support and Logistics: Strategies and Recommendations for System-Scale Studies in a Changing Environment*, in October 2003. Copies of the report were available at the 2003 SEARCH Open Science Meeting, 2003 AGU Fall Meeting, and other relevant meetings. Approximately 1,500 copies have been distributed to-date in response to requests or to identified individuals and organizations. The report is available as a PDF download on the ARCUS website (http://www.arcus.org/Logistics/03_report.html).

1.2. Logistics Internet Resources; Arctic Logistics Information and Support (ALIAS)

Designed and developed ALIAS, an Internet-based logistics support resource, to serve as a primary access point and comprehensive information source to help researchers to assess the feasibility of working in a specific area or on a specific research platform, plan the conduct of research, view current research and research support resources, and make useful scientific and logistics contacts in support of planned research efforts. Specific activities included:

Community Guidance—Convened an 8 member ALIAS advisory group composed of representatives from the Forum of Arctic Research Operators (FARO) and the Arctic Ocean Sciences Board (AOSB) and representing a variety of international arctic research organizations. Presented information about the ALIAS project at 9 national and international science meetings and met with numerous logistics providers between 2001–2005.

ALIAS Website—Worked with stakeholders and managers to add information to ALIAS website (http://www.arcus.org/Logistics/about_alias.html) for 40 research stations and sites and 47 vessels involved in arctic research; information included ownership and management, capabilities, scientific equipment and space, communications and data equipment, scheduling, and other information. Connected ALIAS with the VECO Polar Resources database and ARCUS' Directory of Arctic Researchers through the use of dynamic linking. In 2005, as online search capabilities matured, ARCUS, in consultation with and with approval from NSF program officers, suspended further development of the ALIAS project and reprogrammed the funds to Task 1.8, Community Survey to Identify Arctic Research Data Coordination and Data Management Needs.

1.3 Planning for Integrated Arctic Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

Building on activities funded under the prior Cooperative Agreement, ARCUS continued activities and communications with the broad arctic research and GIS communities in support of advancing research planning and analysis in the Arctic by using geospatial concepts and tools. Major activities included: creation of an Arctic GIS Website, convening an Arctic Geospatial Information Infrastructure (GII) meeting and a North Slope GIS planning meeting, development of a GIS database of multi-agency arctic observing activities for the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC), and other community activities, detailed below. The community planning activities under this Cooperative Agreement task, while keeping pace with technological and conceptual advances in GIS and cyberinfrastructure, have resulted in coordinated development of community GIS efforts to ensure that activities integrate and build on existing efforts while focusing on community-wide science and logistics priorities. Specific activities included:

Arctic GIS Website—Developed, launched (in February 2004), and continued maintenance and expansion of an Arctic GIS Website, which was built with broad community input as an information resource for GIS/GII efforts. The website (<http://www.arcus.org/gis/index.html>) includes information from relevant GIS meetings and workshops, an annotated website directory, and other resources. Members of the arctic research and GIS communities continue to provide updates and additions to the website, resulting in an important information portal to arctic GIS activities and resources.

Arctic GIS Planning Meeting—Worked with Renée Crain, meeting chair, to convene a half-day meeting on Arctic GIS Planning, held 30 October 2003, in Seattle, Washington. The Arctic GIS Planning meeting, attended by 31 participants, focused on next steps and priorities for implementing improvements to Arctic GII.

- Arranged meeting logistics, assisted in preparation of participant materials, and provided on-site meeting support.
- Developed meeting webpages with background information, agenda, presentations, participant list, summary and recommendations, and relevant links (http://www.arcus.org/gis/2003_Planning.html).
- The meeting resulted in recommendations for planning priorities, including development of: (1) an Internet Map Server or other visualization tool with NSF project locations for lower-end users, (2) a circumarctic framework layer GIS server; (3) regional or topical GIS nodes for research; (4) more sophisticated visualization and analysis tool for science users; (5) an Arctic Geospatial Portal; and (6) distributed Metadata and Data Clearinghouses. Various groups in the arctic GIS and research communities followed on these recommendations through development of NSF-funded projects, community proposals, and other coordination and planning activities.

North Slope GIS Meeting—Worked with Allison Gaylord of Nuna Technologies, meeting chair, to convene a one-day meeting on North Slope GIS Efforts in Support of Research and Logistics, held 31 October 2003, in Seattle, Washington. The goal of this meeting was to survey and discuss synergistic GIS efforts with respect to research and logistic support on the North Slope of Alaska; 20 people participated in the meeting, which included presentations and discussions on the development of various GIS initiatives on the North Slope, and assessed the progress that has been made in the context of recommendations from the 2001 Arctic GIS Workshop (http://www.arcus.org/gis/2001_Workshop.html).

- Worked with meeting chair to arrange meeting logistics, prepare participant materials, and provide on-site meeting support.
- Developed meeting webpages with background information, agenda, presentations, participant list, and summary and recommendations (http://www.arcus.org/gis/2003_North_Slope.html).
- Three key recommendations from this meeting, which complement those from the Arctic GIS Planning Meeting (above), included development of: (1) multiple regional nodes for North Slope GIS activities; (2) a transparent gateway (i.e., starting portal) as umbrella for nodes; and (3) an Arctic Geospatial Information Infrastructure Forum. Various groups in the arctic GIS and research communities followed on these recommendations to advance coordinated efforts in North Slope GIS activities.

GIS Database and Maps for IARPC Arctic Observing Network Report—ARCUS developed a GIS of U.S. federal observing projects currently taking place in the Arctic to provide spatially accurate maps for the 2007 Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) report, *Arctic Observing Network (AON): Toward a U.S. Contribution to Pan-Arctic Observing*. The GIS database provides a dynamic system that was used to capture, store, manage, and present locations and associated attributes on myriad arctic observing activities for 12 federal agencies, including all NSF-funded Arctic Observing Network

(AON) projects; 13 full-color maps were created from the GIS for inclusion in the IARPC AON Report.

- Worked with IARPC and NSF staff to determine the scope of work and overall structure of GIS database, including expected data layers to be included.
- Gathered and organized spatial data for current federal observing activities on atmospheric, hydrologic, cryospheric, terrestrial, sea ice and oceanographic, paleologic, and human dimensions efforts in the Arctic by working with all participating agencies, including: Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP), Cooperative Arctic Data and Information Service (CADIS), Bureau of Indian Affairs (BIA), Bureau of Land Management (BLM), Department of Defense (DOD), Federal Aviation Administration (FAA), National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), National Park Service (NPS), National Science Foundation (NSF) and NSF investigators, U.S. Department of Agriculture (USDA), U.S. Forest Service (USFS), U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS), and U.S. Geological Survey (USGS).
- Reconciled and crosschecked data with the contributing sources and assessed for accuracy, ensuring the highest quality data possible before inclusion in the database.
- Imported all geographic location data into GIS (ArcGIS 9.2 software system), creating a dynamic database of geographic coordinates and 64 corresponding GIS database files.
- Developed, in collaboration with Allison Gaylord of Nuna Technologies, map graphic display characteristics and symbology that were utilized to create 13 full-color print-quality maps depicting observing activities in the Arctic.
- In addition to the GIS of current U.S. federal observing activities, ARCUS created GIS layers of the SEARCH observing priorities as depicted in the 2005 SEARCH Implementation Workshop Report (see section 1.4a). ARCUS digitized all locations included in the report maps to produce GIS layers of the observing activities and locations (atmospheric, hydrologic, cryospheric, terrestrial, sea ice and oceanographic, paleologic, and human dimensions) that were recommended by the SEARCH community as priority observing efforts.

Other Community GIS Activities—Additional activities to support community GIS efforts were accomplished throughout the Cooperative Agreement period, including:

- Continued on-request printing and distribution of *Recommendations for a Geographic Information Infrastructure to Support Arctic Research: Outcomes of the Arctic GIS Workshop* (2001). Report is available online at: http://www.arcus.org/gis/2001_Workshop.html.
- Assisted in coordination activities of an informal working group, chaired by Mark Sorensen of Geographic Planning Collaborative Inc. (GPC), to disseminate and gather community input on a white paper entitled *Arctic Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) for Scientific Research*, which outlined the framework and specifications for an Arctic SDI. Circulated to the arctic research community through relevant listserves and other online forums in 2004, the white paper summarized an Arctic SDI conceptual framework and technical specifications such as portal technologies, metadata, research needs, education and outreach, and implementation issues. The white paper is available on the ARCUS GIS website at: <http://www.arcus.org/gis/background.html>.
- Collaborated with Matt Nolan, University of Alaska Fairbanks, on the use of EarthSLOT, a terrain and data visualization application for education purposes; trained ARCUS staff

person in use of EarthSLOT and created GIS visualization digital “movies” for teachers involved in the ARCUS education program, Teachers and Researchers - Exploring and Collaborating (TREC; see section 3.5).

- Collaborated with members of the arctic GIS community in International Polar Year (IPY) planning and to draft an Arctic GIS IPY Letter of Intent, as part of the IPY effort to survey community efforts in polar science activities in 2005.
- Provided input to agenda development and organizational support for “GIS Jam” sessions at the Alaska Surveying and Mapping Conference held March 2007, in Fairbanks, Alaska; GIS Jam sessions included talks, panels, and sessions on GIS/GII development to advance arctic science, logistics, and education.
- Provided content input to relevant arctic GIS conference sessions, posters, presentations, and outreach events, including those at GIS user conferences and annual Fall AGU conferences.
- Supported collaborative efforts in the arctic GIS community through continued website development, communications, teleconferences, and information dissemination.

1.4a Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) Coordination and Planning

The Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) is an interagency program to understand the causes, connections, and consequences of recent arctic environmental changes, emphasizing their interactions with global climate change and potential impacts on the biosphere, including human social and economic wellbeing.

SEARCH is guided by the SEARCH Science Steering Committee (SSC), the Interagency Program Management Committee (IPMC; formerly Interagency Working Group), and 3 panels—the Observing Change Panel, Understanding Change Panel, and Responding to Change Panel—that advise and aid the SSC in the development of SEARCH implementation. Various working groups (e.g., Data Management, Paleoenvironment, Education and Outreach) provide focused input to individual SEARCH action areas.

Within this Cooperative Agreement period, ARCUS coordinated and convened the first SEARCH Open Science Meeting in October 2003. In early 2005, the SEARCH Science Management Office functions were transitioned from the University of Washington to ARCUS. As the SEARCH Science Management Office, ARCUS has worked with the SEARCH SSC Chair and members, SEARCH Panels, working groups, members of the SEARCH IPMC, and the international arctic research community to implement a number of development and planning activities on behalf of SEARCH.

In this Cooperative Agreement period, SEARCH has advanced from a conceptual framework to an active multi-disciplinary research program, with nearly 70 research projects now funded as SEARCH activities, including projects funded through the NSF Arctic Observing Network (AON) effort, NSF Division of Arctic Sciences programs, and other SEARCH IPMC agencies. Strong collaborations with international programs have expanded SEARCH to a truly pan-arctic effort. With these accomplishments, SEARCH has contributed significantly to our understanding of the nature, extent, and future development of the system-scale change in the Arctic. Specific activities included:

SEARCH Open Science Meeting—ARCUS organized and facilitated the first SEARCH Open Science Meeting (OSM), held 27–30 October 2003, in Seattle, Washington, at which 454 social and natural scientists, policy makers, and stakeholders representing 177 organizations from 18 countries presented and discussed evidence of rapid environmental change in the Arctic.

- Worked with the NSF program manager and the SEARCH Science Steering Committee to select and appoint a 10-member Organizing Committee to advise and oversee meeting planning and implementation.
- Selected the meeting venue; arranged for technical and logistic support and accommodations; coordinated travel and participant arrangements; paid travel costs for invited speakers, Organizing Committee members, other participants receiving travel support, and other meeting and support costs.
- Assisted the Organizing Committee to develop the meeting priorities, structure, focus, and agenda. The agenda included a combination of invited keynote talks, panel discussions, parallel science sessions with contributed talks, and poster sessions.
- Prepared and distributed announcements publicizing the meeting via ArcticInfo, ARCUS website, and hardcopy at various conferences and meetings, including a call for input and suggestions to the meeting agenda, calls for presentation and poster abstracts, and registration and logistics announcements.
- Developed and maintained a SEARCH Open Science Meeting website; prepared and maintained website content, including online registration and abstract submission system, agenda, logistics information, and an online searchable database of submitted oral and poster abstracts.
- Worked with the Organizing Committee to develop a process for assessing and determining merit-based travel support for participants in need of additional funding.
- With guidance from the Organizing Committee and the SEARCH Science Steering Committee, identified and invited 21 keynote speakers and 13 panelists, recruited 16 facilitators, and solicited 76 papers for the parallel science sessions.
- Worked with interested organizations and groups to coordinate 23 side meetings before, during, and after the Open Science Meeting. These side meetings represented a variety of topical, organizational, and disciplinary foci, and ranged from small groups holding working meetings on specific science topics to large town meetings held to gather input on international programs.
- Solicited media interest and organized a media campaign related to SEARCH research findings; worked with the Organizing Committee and media liaisons from NSF, University of Washington, and NASA to engage print, radio, and Internet media and to arrange a press event held at the conference; worked with the telecommunications company Vision Net, Inc., to provide press event and plenary sessions to the public via streaming video. Significant press interest and several stories resulted, which are available online at: <http://www.arcus.org/SEARCH/meetings/2003/mediacoverage.php>.
- Worked with NSF publications office and other arctic organizations and programs to gather outreach and informational materials for display and distribution at the conference.
- Prepared final meeting materials including agenda, venue and travel information, participant list, preliminary abstracts; provided information via website and participant notebooks with CD-ROM.
- Managed the conference activities and provided staff support for the 4-day conference.

- Developed and published on the website post-meeting materials and information, including final agenda, abstracts, powerpoint presentations, participant list, compilation of media coverage, and edited video of the sessions.
- Developed and administered merit-based student scholarship program (detailed as separate task, see section 1.4b. SEARCH Open Science Meeting Student Support).
- Worked with science session co-chairs and Organizing Committee to prepare the final conference report, *Proceedings of the SEARCH Open Science Meeting, 27–30 October 2003, Seattle, Washington*, which includes an introductory executive summary, summary of the parallel science sessions, presentation and poster abstracts, and participant list. The final report was printed and distributed to meeting participants and interested parties, and is available in hardcopy and online at:
<http://www.arcus.org/search/resources/reportsandscienceplans.php>.

Transition to SEARCH Science Management Office—In early 2005, the SEARCH Science Management Office function transitioned from the University of Washington to ARCUS. Concurrently, the SSC Chair position transitioned from James Morison, University of Washington, to Peter Schlosser, Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory. ARCUS worked with the SEARCH SSC chair and members, NSF program manager, prior SMO, and the SEARCH Interagency Working Group to plan and implement the transition of other SMO activities during 2005, including:

- Support the identification of research and organizational priorities.
- Develop processes for community input and development.
- Workshop and conference organization and planning.
- Support scientific program planning and implementation.
- Coordination with the International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC) and other related national and international efforts.
- Public outreach and education efforts, including transition of the SEARCH website.

SEARCH Website—As part of the initial responsibilities of the SEARCH Science Management Office, ARCUS developed and launched a new SEARCH website in March 2005. The SEARCH website provides a comprehensive and up-to-date resource for information on: SEARCH science and projects, meetings and activities, coordination structure and membership, related national and international programs, and other timely information for SEARCH scientists, agency personnel, and the public. The website is at <http://www.arcus.org/search/index.php>.

- Completed initial framework website, including redesign, framework pages for content, and development of functionality.
- Worked with the University of Washington SEARCH office to transition content to ARCUS-maintained website.
- Compiled and created updated content for the website, including several SEARCH science pages featuring latest research and science news.
- Worked iteratively with SEARCH SSC chair, the SSC, and other user communities to refine and build website content and functionality in preparation for public launching.
- Launched new SEARCH website March 2005.
- Continued updates and refinements to website content and functionality.

SEARCH Science Steering Committee (SSC), Panels, and Working Group Support—

A primary responsibility of the SEARCH Science Management Office is support of SEARCH SSC, panels, and working group activities. The SEARCH SSC guides the implementation of SEARCH, maintaining the program's focus and direction, identifying areas of linkage between the individual SEARCH implementation areas, defining new critical questions, and serving as a connection between SEARCH and other programs. The Observing Change, Understanding Change, and Responding to Change panels and working groups (Data Management, Paleoenvironment, and Education and Outreach) work with the SSC to guide implementation of specific SEARCH action areas. Activities and accomplishments have included:

SSC Membership Rotation—Worked with the SEARCH SSC Chair, members, and IPMC to implement scheduled membership rotation for the SSC to ensure broad disciplinary representation.

SSC Meetings and Teleconferences—Worked with SSC Chair to organize, prepare for, and convene SSC teleconferences and annual SSC meetings. Each SSC meeting provided opportunities to review and stimulate progress on the program's development and implementation as science and agency priorities evolved. Discussion topics included SEARCH science, agency planning and implementation of SEARCH activities, and coordination with relevant national and international arctic efforts; participants included SSC members, panel representatives, agency personnel, and other invited participants from SEARCH and relevant communities. Products of these meetings are available on the ARCUS website. In-person SSC meetings have convened annually:

- November 2005 in Fairbanks, Alaska
http://www.arcus.org/search/meetings/2005/ssc_fairbanks/index.php
- November 2006 in Arlington, Virginia
<http://www.arcus.org/search/meetings/2006/ssc/index.php>
- November 2007 in Washington, DC
<http://www.arcus.org/search/meetings/2007/ssc/index.php>

Appoint Panels and Working Groups—Worked with SSC Chair and members to create and appoint 3 implementation panels (Observing Change Panel, Understanding Change Panel, and Responding to Change Panel) and working groups on Data Management, Paleoenvironment, and Education and Outreach.

Support Panel and Working Group Activities—Worked with SSC, panels, and working groups to facilitate panel and working group activities, including teleconferences and input into SEARCH planning meetings and activities.

Additional Support Activities—Support activities such as travel support for the SEARCH SSC Chair, maintaining email listserves and groups, facilitating communication between the SEARCH organizational structure, and assisting in development of SEARCH presentations, posters, and related materials for the SEARCH SSC Chair.

SEARCH Project Catalog—Since SEARCH science is implemented through a variety of mechanisms, including projects funded through NSF's Arctic Observing Network (AON) effort, other NSF Division of Arctic Sciences programs, and through other SEARCH IPMC agencies, a comprehensive information portal to SEARCH science efforts is critical to overall SEARCH planning and coordination.

The SEARCH Project Catalog, available at:

<http://www.arcus.org/search/catalog/public/catalogsearch.php>, is an online database-driven catalog of SEARCH-relevant projects launched to track and communicate SEARCH-funded and SEARCH-related research projects, initiatives, and programs. The online project database contains information on: project personnel, project abstract, funding agencies, keywords, regions and locations studied, SEARCH activity areas, weblinks to data, and other relevant information. The database interface allows users to browse, search, and submit project information. There are currently 69 projects in the Project Catalog, which is under continual development and improvement as additional projects and user functionality is added.

SEARCH for DAMOCLES International Coordination—The SEARCH for DAMOCLES (S4D) partnership was established through a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) between SEARCH and the European Union-funded Developing Arctic Modeling and Observing Capabilities for Long-term Environmental Studies (DAMOCLES) project. DAMOCLES is a European consortium of 45 institutions working to develop an arctic atmosphere-ice-ocean observing system. SEARCH and DAMOCLES share several scientific objectives, including observations of the Arctic Ocean sea-ice and key atmospheric processes, assimilation of observations with models, and assessment of environmental and human impacts. Opportunities presented by the SEARCH for DAMOCLES (S4D) partnership include enhanced and coordinated acquisition of pan-arctic data sets, dissemination of results, and public awareness. In addition to providing coordination and support in the development of the S4D MOU and scope of work, ARCUS provided organizational support to the international steering committee and the 5 working groups (WG) that oversee S4D activities:

- WG1: System Design/Observations and Integration—Guides synchronization of observing strategies, modeling and analysis approaches, and related activities.
- WG2: Evaluation/Modeling and Understanding—Guides coordinated modeling projects, evaluation of model designs and parameterizations to improve modeling capability, and related activities.
- WG3: Synthesis/Exploitation of Knowledge—Guides strategies for coordinated synthesis, dissemination, transfer, and utilization of research results, and related activities.
- WG4: Response and Education/Outreach—Guides strategies for stakeholder-driven guidance of research activities, community-based observation networks, education and outreach activities, and related activities.
- WG5: Data Management—Guides coordination of policies on data formats, catalogs, archives, and related activities.

ARCUS also supported reciprocal participation of program representatives at appropriate meetings to coordinate activities, including

- 2007 SEARCH SSC meeting (see above);
- 2006 and 2007 DAMOCLES General Assembly Meetings (http://www.damocles-eu.org/article_370.shtml); and
- October 2007 S4D Modeling workshop (<http://www.arcus.org/search/internationalsearch/meetings-and-activities.php>).

International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC)—As a result of international interest and discussions at the 2003 SEARCH Open Science Meeting, the Arctic Ocean Sciences Board (AOSB) and the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) formed ISAC to support international participation in SEARCH efforts. ARCUS has supported coordination between the U.S. SEARCH program and ISAC planning by coordinating input from the SEARCH SSC to ISAC planning activities, and coordinating reciprocal participation of program representatives at appropriate meetings.

SEARCH Implementation Workshop, May 2005—ARCUS planned, organized, and convened the SEARCH Implementation Workshop, held 23–25 May 2005, in Lansdowne, Virginia, to establish priorities for the next steps of the implementation of SEARCH. The report resulting from this meeting guides the science community and agencies in SEARCH planning, including that for the International Polar Year (IPY) 2007–2008. The 95 workshop participants included members of the SEARCH SSC; the Observing Change, Understanding Change, and Responding to Change panels; the SEARCH IPMC; as well as other invited participants. The workshop was organized with a combination of plenary discussions and working group sessions.

- Worked with SEARCH SSC chair and members, SEARCH panels, and NSF program manager to develop focus, structure, and meeting materials; supported preparation and distribution of position papers outlining priority implementation activities from Observing Change, Understanding Change, and Responding to Change panels.
- Developed and maintained meeting website pages, including participant list, agenda, background materials, and community input tools, such as online bulletin boards (<http://www.arcus.org/search/meetings/2005/siw/index.php>).
- Coordinated logistics of workshop and supported meeting process.
- Coordinated drafting, review, revision, and production of final workshop report, *Study of Environmental Arctic Change: Plans for Implementation During the International Polar Year and Beyond: Report of the SEARCH Implementation Workshop, May 23–25, 2005* (available at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/meetings/2005/siw/report.php>), which details SEARCH implementation priorities for immediate planning in preparation for IPY and for an Arctic Observing Network, and to provide a perspective on SEARCH beyond the program's immediate needs and priorities. The report was cited in the 2006 NSF IPY Program Solicitation (NSF 06-534) and was a major source for the recent Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) report *Arctic Observing Network: Toward a U.S. Contribution to Pan-Arctic Observing*.

Arctic Observation Integration Workshops 2007—ARCUS planned, organized, and convened a series of 3 workshops to advance planning and implementation of an integrated Arctic Observation System that is responsive to the critical scientific issues of environmental arctic change. The Arctic Observation Integration Workshops, held 17–20 March 2008, in Palisades, NY, included: a 1.5-day NSF Arctic Observing Network (AON) investigator meeting; a half-day international workshop, jointly sponsored by the AON and SEARCH for DAMOCLES (S4D) programs, on optimizing deployment of Lagrangian platforms; and a 1.5-day workshop, jointly sponsored by the NSF AON program, the NSF Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program, and S4D, to improve understanding of recent arctic sea ice change. Over 70 participants attended the workshop series.

- Recruited members to serve on Organizing Committees for each workshop as well as an overall Workshop Coordination Committee; worked with each committee as appropriate to develop workshop focus, structure, and meeting materials; developed and maintained meeting website pages, including participant list, agenda, and background materials (<http://www.arcus.org/search/Meetings/2008/aow/index.php>).
- Coordinated logistics of workshops and supported meeting process.
- Coordinated drafting, review, revision, and production of final workshop report, *Arctic Observation Integration: Workshops Report*, available online as a PDF at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/meetings/2008/aow/report.php>. The report outlines short-term and long-term recommendations underscoring 3 central themes that emerged from workshop presentations and discussions: (1) understanding the extraordinary seasonal retreat of sea ice observed in 2007, (2) addressing the challenge of integrating different observation efforts into a system that serves science as well as broader society and key stakeholder groups, and (3) identifying scientific and programmatic gaps and next steps for observing, understanding, and responding to arctic environmental change with emphasis on high-amplitude, unexpected changes. Distributed printed copies of the report to workshop participants, other interested individuals, and on request.

1.4b SEARCH Open Science Meeting Student Support

The SEARCH Open Science Meeting (OSM) Organizing Committee asked ARCUS to develop a student scholarship program to ensure the rigorous and productive participation of young investigators in the SEARCH OSM.

- Developed and administered merit-based student scholarship program to encourage the participation of young investigators; funded a portion of participation costs for 38 undergraduate and graduate students representing 21 institutions and 5 countries. Students represented over one dozen scientific disciplines, including anthropology, biology, ecology, economics, hydrology, geography, geophysics, and natural resource management. All supported students presented a poster during the meeting.
- Managed student poster contest, including the development of judging criteria, selection of judges, and presentation of poster contest results at the conference. ARCUS partnered with the Arctic Institute of North America (AINA) to offer awards to 3 competition winners. The winners received support to attend a relevant conference on the Arctic and their work was highlighted at the 2004 *Arctic Forum* in Washington, D.C. They also received a 2-year Arctic Institute of North America membership, which included a subscription to the interdisciplinary journal *ARCTIC*.
- Worked with the Alaska Native Science Commission (ANSC) to insure participation of Alaska Native students; 5 Alaska Native students were sponsored.

1.5 Planning for Bering Sea Research: Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST)

For the past several years the NSF Arctic Sciences Section has supported the Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST)—a planning process to initiate collaborative studies of this productive subarctic marine ecosystem. Since March 2003, ARCUS has provided organizational support and coordination of activities for the BEST science planning process, including support for the development and publication of the 2004 *BEST Science Plan*, the 2005 *BEST Implementation Plan*, and coordination with other organizations as the program moved into implementation.

BEST priorities for research were included in the Fall 2005 NSF Arctic Sciences Section Announcement of Opportunity (<http://www.nsf.gov/pubs/2005/nsf05618/nsf05618.htm>) and in a special program solicitation in December 2006 (http://www.nsf.gov/publications/pub_summ.jsp?ods_key=nsf07533); awards through these opportunities were announced in July 2006 and September 2007. The funded BEST projects are the NSF contribution to a special research partnership with the North Pacific Research Board (NPRB) to support a comprehensive, vertically integrated investigation of the ecosystem of the eastern continental shelf of the Bering Sea. ARCUS provided organizational support to the program; specific activities included:

BEST Science Plan—In close consultation with George Hunt, leader of the BEST planning group, developed and published the 2004 *Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) Science Plan*. Organized and convened a 23-participant planning workshop (Seattle, March 2003) and 3 town hall meetings to review and discuss drafts of the science plan (Seattle, October 2003; San Francisco, December 2003; Honolulu, February 2004); distributed the draft plan for community and invited reviews; with oversight by the planning group, revised the draft science plan in response to comments received; published 1,000 copies of the science plan in October 2004; distributed copies at relevant arctic-focused meetings and in response to requests. The *Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) Science Plan* is also available as a PDF download on the ARCUS website (<http://www.arcus.org/Bering/reports/index.html>).

BEST Website—Developed, launched, maintained, and updated a section of the ARCUS website designed to support the BEST planning process, including information on previous and upcoming meetings and downloads of reports and background materials (<http://www.arcus.org/Bering/index.html>).

BEST Science Steering Committee Support—Assisted with the appointment and convening of a BEST Science Steering Committee (SSC); supported electronic meetings and interactions of the committee for the preparation of a draft implementation plan; planned, coordinated, convened, and provided staff and travel support for SSC meetings in May 2005 and July 2006. Coordinated travel arrangements and provided materials and travel support for PIs or representatives of the BEST SSC to attend a number of relevant meetings, including the Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) Open Science Meeting (Seattle, October 2003), the American Geophysical Union Fall meeting (San Francisco, December 2003), the American Society for Limnology and Oceanography Ocean Sciences Meetings (Honolulu, February 2004 and Santa Fe, New Mexico, February 2007), the PICES-Ecosystems of Sub-arctic Seas (ESSAS) workshops (St. Petersburg, Russia, June 2006 and Hakodate, Japan, June 2007), the Calista Elders Council (Bethel, Alaska, January 2007), the Alaska Marine Science Symposium (Anchorage, Alaska, January 2007), and the Alaska Forum on the Environment (Anchorage, Alaska, February 2007).

BEST Open Implementation Workshop—Worked with Dr. Hunt and the Global Ocean Ecosystem Dynamics (GLOBEC) project office to plan and convene the BEST Implementation Workshop in conjunction with the GLOBEC Symposium on Climate Variability and Sub-arctic Marine Ecosystems in Victoria, B.C., Canada, May 2005. The

workshop was designed to inform stakeholders and the scientific community about the opportunities for climate-related research in the Bering Sea, particularly research opportunities in the BEST program and to elicit comments on the draft BEST Implementation Plan. To ensure that the implementation plan incorporated the concerns and interests from a broad constituency of researchers, resource managers, fishers, and Alaska Native communities, participants from a wide array of disciplines and backgrounds were invited to the workshop. Coordinated travel funding provided for U.S. participants in the symposium, including 4 graduate students. Developed and maintained a webpage to support the meeting planning and make its products available (<http://www.arcus.org/Bering/meetings/oiw/index.html>).

BEST Implementation Plan—Provided staff support to the chair and Science Steering Committee members for the development of the *BEST Implementation Plan*, which was published in September 2005 and is available as a PDF download on the ARCUS website (<http://www.arcus.org/Bering/reports/index.html>). Coordinated and supported drafting process, including integration of a social sciences research component (see section 2.3.4), review of draft plan, revision, publication, and ongoing distribution.

Climate Change & the Bering Ecosystem Meeting—In close collaboration with the BEST SSC, the NSF program manager, and other agency representatives, ARCUS planned, convened, and staffed a meeting in July 2006 of multiple entities with research interests in the Bering Sea, including the BEST SSC, the Bering Interagency Working Group, and the Bering Interagency Oversight Group. The meeting was held on the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) campus in Seattle, Washington; 34 invited participants and about 15 additional NOAA personnel attended.

Principal Investigators' Meetings—Planned, convened, and staffed a meeting of funded BEST Principal Investigators and representatives of the BEST SSC in September 2006 in Arlington, VA, to coordinate the development of an integrated research program and to guide fieldwork. In close collaboration with the NSF program officer and the staff of the North Pacific Research Board, planned, coordinated, convened, and staffed a joint Principal Investigators' meeting in Seattle, WA, 17–19 September 2007. In collaboration with the chief scientists and Coast Guard personnel, planned, coordinated, convened, and staffed a series of cruise planning meetings in Seattle, 29–30 November 2007, for BEST investigators working on the USCGC *Healy* in 2008.

1.6 Workshop, to be Determined

- No activity.

1.7 Reprinting of the SEARCH Brochure

In 2001, ARCUS developed, printed and distributed 3,500 copies of a short informational brochure, *SEARCH: The Study of Environmental Arctic Change*. At the request of NSF, 1,000 additional copies were printed in June 2004, and 300 copies were sent directly to NSF at their request. The reprinting of the brochure was considered a part of the SEARCH Science Management Office activities, and the cost is included in the budget for activity 1.4a Study of

Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) Coordination and Planning. Distribution of hard copies and availability of PDF download is continuing.

1.8 Community Survey to Identify Arctic Research Data Coordination and Data Management Needs

Various arctic planning activities, conferences, and meetings have identified a need for improved information about arctic research data coordination and management needs and problems—specifically for projects and programs that are interdisciplinary, multi-institutional, interagency, or international in scope.

With approval from the NSF Program Officer, ARCUS used funds originally designated for the ALIAS project (see section 1.2) to begin work toward the development of an Arctic Spatial Data Infrastructure (ASDI). As part of its contributions to this effort, ARCUS developed a community survey to assess community perspectives on needs, readiness, and resources for ASDI using an online survey system. Unfortunately, ARCUS and collaborators have not been awarded the funding expected through a SGER proposal submitted in December 2005 to implement the survey and advance this effort.

As part of efforts in community planning and development related to arctic data management and coordination, ARCUS provided travel support for the ARCUS Director of Programs as an invited participant at the Building Effective Virtual Organizations workshop in Washington, D.C., 14–16 January 2008.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

Work accomplished under this task includes a number of activities for the Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program and the Arctic Social Sciences Program, as well as the development of information and outreach materials for the Arctic Section as a whole.

2.1 Arctic Section Science Materials

Arctic Science Discoveries Poster—At the request of the NSF Arctic Sciences Section, ARCUS developed and produced a poster describing Arctic Sciences Section activities and programs for use in the NSF Office of Polar Programs (OPP) informational display. Multiple laminated copies of this poster, *Arctic Science Discoveries*, have been provided in large format and displayed at many conferences and venues since 2002; small “handout” copies and a PDF also have been provided.

Arctic Science Education Poster—Developed and produced a poster on arctic science education activities sponsored by the NSF Arctic Sciences Section, for inclusion in the NSF OPP informational display and use at relevant meetings and conferences since 2003. Multiple laminated copies of the poster in large format and a PDF have been provided.

Arctic Sciences Section Brochure—Prepared a design concept for an Arctic Sciences Section brochure at the request of NSF staff. Further work on a brochure was not requested.

Guidelines for Improved Cooperation—Coordinated community outreach and review for *Guidelines for Improved Cooperation between Arctic Researchers and Northern Communities*, drafted by the Arctic Sciences Section of the Office of Polar Programs at the National Science Foundation and the Barrow Arctic Science Consortium, with the input of the Alaska Eskimo Whaling Commission, North Slope Borough Department of Wildlife Management and the Alaska Native Science Commission.

- Developed and published set of web pages to present content of draft report.
- Published online survey to gather feedback on the draft document and forwarded comments to NSF Program Officer.
- Printed 100 copies of the document for a 2004 Alaska Native Science Commission meeting in Anchorage, Alaska.
- Posted PDF of draft report online (<http://www.arcus.org/guidelines/document.html>).

Arctic Section Proposal Target Date Survey—Community discussion about the timing of a new proposal deadline for the NSF Arctic Sciences Section led ARCUS to develop and conduct an online survey of the U.S. arctic research community from January–April 2005 to get feedback on researchers’ recommendations on the best timing for an annual deadline in future years.

- Developed set of web pages for online survey, including a graphical online results page.
- 158 members of the research community submitted the online survey, and results were forwarded to the NSF Arctic Sciences Section.

2.2 Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program Coordination

The NSF Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program is a multidisciplinary program to understand changes in the arctic system and what these changes imply for the future. The ARCSS Program supports fieldwork and research that synthesizes existing data and knowledge to advance understanding of the arctic system and its role in the global system and society.

In this Cooperative Agreement period, ARCSS Program research has continued to build on a solid foundation of more than a decade of observation, modeling, and process studies and evolved toward an increasingly integrative and synthetic, rather than disciplinary, approach to studying the arctic system. Using this synthetic approach, researchers involved in organized ARCSS efforts, which include Synthesis of Arctic System Science (SASS), Study of Northern Alaska Coastal System (SNACS), Freshwater Integration Study (FWI), Western Shelf-Basin Interactions (SBI), and Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC), have identified important gaps in knowledge and community research priorities.

ARCUS has provided community science management and coordination of activities for the ARCSS Program since 1991. Over the period of this Cooperative Agreement, major tasks under this activity include: ARCSS coordination, organizing the ARCSS All-Hands Workshop, supporting the development of a science management office for the Human Dimensions of the Arctic (HARC) research initiative, and publishing a report on the arctic hydrological cycle.

2.2.1 ARCSS Coordination

During the past 7 years, the ARCSS Program has progressed through several community-driven transitions, evolving from a disciplinary component structure to thematic research initiatives and synthesis activities aimed at achieving system-level understanding of the Arctic. With guidance from the ARCSS Committee (AC) and the NSF ARCSS Program Director, ARCUS assumed the role of the ARCSS Science Management Office (SMO) in 2004 and has facilitated these changes by providing support and coordination to the ARCSS research community. Program coordination activities have been designed to sustain an effective system-science effort and foster high levels of community input and strong interdisciplinary collaboration. Specific activities included:

ARCSS Committee Support—ARCSS Program development is facilitated by the ARCSS Committee (AC), which takes a proactive approach on behalf of the research community. Appointed by ARCUS, the AC is not an official NSF advisory committee but offers a mechanism through which NSF can stay informed of community priorities. The AC comprises investigators participating in ARCSS research and others who bring broader scientific viewpoints and expertise. Members of the committee serve 3-year terms, allowing for changes in perspective and priorities as the research program evolves. During this reporting period, ARCUS performed numerous activities in support of the AC:

Membership Rotation—Coordinated changes in membership of the 11-member AC. Recruited new AC chair, Jonathan Overpeck of the University of Arizona Tucson, to replace outgoing chair Jack Kruse of the University of Alaska Anchorage in 2002, and then Josh Schimel of the University of California Santa Barbara to replace Jonathan Overpeck in 2006.

- Annually reviewed the composition of the AC, with the AC chair and the NSF Program Director, in the context of new priorities, representations of key programs, and disciplinary perspectives and expertise. Selected and appointed new members to replace outgoing members.
- Worked with the AC to select and convene an ARCSS Executive Committee. The Executive Committee consists of a subset of members of the AC and works closely with the AC chair and SMO to provide leadership for ARCSS science planning activities.

ARCSS Committee Meetings and Teleconferences—Worked with the AC chair to develop materials and agendas for 11 face-to-face AC meetings, which provided an opportunity for members to discuss ARCSS Program science activities, priorities, future directions, and opportunities. Also provided venue and travel arrangements for these meetings, funded travel costs for AC members, and provided on-site coordination and support. General information about each of these meetings is provided below. Detailed meeting information is posted on the ARCSS website at:

http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/arcss_meetings.html.

- November 2001, in Salt Lake City, UT. Discussions focused on the future directions of the ARCSS Program, plans for the second ARCSS Program All-Hands Workshop (see section 2.2.2), and other activities to promote integration of ARCSS research; 21 participants.
- October 2002, in Arlington, VA. Included reports from ARCSS component groups, after which the AC began to formulate a plan for broader arctic system synthesis; 31 participants.
- March 2003, in Tuscon, AZ. Included reports on ARCSS components and discussion of issues surrounding coordination and implementation of science plans; 22 participants.
- October 2003, in Seattle, WA. Held in conjunction with the SEARCH Open Science Meeting. Discussions focused on timelines for the science plan and implementation guidelines, updates from the Big Sky Synthesis Retreat (see Synthesis Efforts section, below) and Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC: see section 2.2.3), and planning for a second synthesis retreat; 12 participants.
- February 2004, in Boulder, CO. Discussions outlined a new ARCSS science plan and creation of an implementation strategy. The committee also discussed the 2003 Synthesis Retreat and plans for the 2004 retreat. Guest speakers were invited to discuss ideas to better incorporate modelers into the ARCSS Program and strategies for ARCSS data management; 18 participants.
- March 2005, in Arlington, VA. Discussions outlined the new ARCSS process and structure, as well as future planning priorities and outreach activities; 23 participants.
- October 2005, in Arlington, VA. Discussions focused on future ARCSS Program activities; 13 participants.
- March 2006, in Seattle, WA. In addition to discussions on program science activities, priorities, and future directions, there was an open session with presentations from community groups and talks on science goals and questions, key unknowns, and future priorities and activities; 29 participants.
- November 2006, in Seattle, WA. Participants discussed the transition of the ARCSS Program from a focus on synthesis to targeted thematic efforts addressing arctic

system issues. The meeting also included updates on the ARCSS Program, science advocacy, data and modeling activities, and ARCSS community development and support; 20 participants.

- May 2007, in Washington, DC. Included programmatic updates from NSF Arctic Division staff and updates on ARCSS research activities from AC members. Other discussion topics included the status of research efforts, planning for an arctic-wide science meeting, development of an Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory, status and priorities within HARC, and community science planning needs. Invited guests also presented reports on the Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH), ARCSS data management activities, and International Arctic Research Center (IARC) strategic planning; 19 participants.
- October 2007, in Alexandria, VA. In addition to discussion of program science activities, priorities, and future directions, the meeting included an open session soliciting community input on ARCSS goals and priorities; 54 participants.
- Teleconferences: Planned and convened regular teleconference meetings with members of the AC, NSF representatives, and the research community to review ongoing planning efforts and to discuss directions for the ARCSS Program.

Travel for ARCSS Committee Chair—Provided the AC chair with a stipend and travel funds to participate in ARCSS-related meetings and workshops.

Communities of Practice (Co-oPs)—Over this Cooperative Agreement period, ARCUS worked with the AC and NSF to develop a science planning process focused on system-level research that fosters stronger interdisciplinary collaboration. Development of this new process led to the formation of Communities of Practice (Co-oPs)—groups of researchers organized around a set of arctic system science questions. Co-oPs work with the AC, ARCUS, and the broader research community to develop science questions that align with and advance ARCSS Program goals.

eTown Meetings—ARCUS worked with the AC to plan and organize 7 online eTown Meetings involving more than 270 community members in the development of Co-oP concepts. ARCUS facilitated these open, online meetings, which enabled participation in live audio web-conferencing, online presentations, polling, and text chat.

Co-oP Web Resources—Provided Co-oP web resources, including an online form for submitting Co-oP concept papers, email listserves, and eMeeting support (<http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/cop.html>).

Other Co-oP Support—ARCUS coordinated meeting space for use for by the newly formed and emerging Co-oPs during the 2005 Fall American Geophysical Union Meeting in San Francisco, CA. The space also allowed for meetings of opportunity among ARCSS project investigators.

Synthesis Efforts—In 2004, building on nearly 15 years of observation, modeling, and process studies, the ARCSS Program entered a synthesis-driven phase aimed at achieving system level understanding of the Arctic. ARCUS has worked with the ARCSS Committee, the NSF Program Director, and the ARCSS research community to develop priorities for, plan, and undertake synthesis activities. Specific activities included:

2003 ARCSS Synthesis Retreat—In August 2003, ARCUS planned, organized, convened, and staffed an ARCSS Synthesis Retreat in Big Sky, MT. The purpose of the retreat was to begin distilling and integrating current knowledge into a more holistic perspective of the arctic system. The 30 participants represented a diverse array of disciplines. Retreat discussions ranged from debates about defining the arctic system and its major components to analyses of the relationships among these components. The retreat was an important step in the ARCSS Program shift from component-oriented research to a primary emphasis on scientific synthesis.

- Collected, assembled, and distributed key background readings for retreat participants; developed, updated, and maintained a webpage to support meeting organization, communications, and document review and revision (http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/2003_Retreat/index.html); supported participant travel.
- Coordinated and provided support for a writing group to develop and publish a scholarly paper reporting the retreat findings (Overpeck et al. 2005. Arctic system on a trajectory to a new, seasonally ice-free state. EOS 86:309-316).

2004 ARCSS Synthesis Retreat—ARCUS planned, organized, convened, and staffed a 2nd ARCSS Synthesis Retreat, held August 2004, in Tahoe City, CA. More than 30 scientists and graduate students representing a wide variety of scientific disciplines participated in the weeklong science retreat, which was designed to begin assembling a synthesized system perspective of the region, its components and processes, and the linkages among them.

- Developed and implemented a community synthesis survey in advance of the retreat to gather input from the scientific community about what scientific synthesis is and how ARCSS synthesis can be effectively implemented.
- Collected, assembled, and distributed 26 key background readings for retreat participants; readings were also made available on the ARCSS website as PDF downloads for broad community use; developed, updated, and maintained a webpage to support meeting organization, communications, and document review and revision (http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/2004_Retreat/index.html); supported participant travel.
- Coordinated and provided support for a writing group from the retreat to develop scholarly papers reporting their findings (Huntington et al. 2007. The impact of human activity in the Arctic on climate and climate impacts. Climatic Change 82:77-92).

Synthesis of Arctic System Science (SASS) Projects—SASS is the ARCSS Program's most recent organized research effort. SASS currently consists of 17 funded projects, with strong linkages to other ARCSS research efforts and related scientific efforts focused on the Arctic. Two SASS-related NSF program solicitations have been released—9 projects addressing system-level science were funded in 2005 (SASS I), and 8 projects were funded in the fall of 2006 (SASS II). Detailed information about the effort and the activities listed below is available on the SASS website:

<http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/sass/>.

- ARCUS worked with the ARCSS Committee to draft recommendations for the scientific focus of a synthesis effort that focuses on advancing our understanding of the arctic system by building on and integrating the wealth of existing data and

- knowledge to advance our understanding of linkages, interactions, and feedbacks among components of the arctic system. Program solicitations titled Synthesis of Arctic System Science were released in November 2004 and December 2005 (http://www.nsf.gov/publications/pub_summ.jsp?ods_key=nsf06523).
- Planned and coordinated an online meeting in November 2005 for SASS I investigators to introduce themselves and their projects, discuss ideas for collaboration and synthesis among projects, and to discuss the type of infrastructure and leadership that would best support the syntheses and integration needs of the SASS I projects as a group.
 - Planned and coordinated an online meeting for SASS I investigators in January 2006 to follow up on the November 2005 online meeting.
 - Planned and coordinated a March 2006 in-person meeting for SASS I investigators in Seattle, WA; 34 participants discussed approaches for synthesis and integration among SASS I projects.
 - Developed, launched, and maintained a SASS website providing information about the effort, individual research projects, and meetings and workshops.

2007 ARCSS Synthesis Workshop—In collaboration with the ARCSS Committee, planned and coordinated an October 2007 meeting in Alexandria, VA, for representatives of SASS projects and other ARCSS-related efforts to discuss project plans and results, and determine methods, approaches, and an organizational structure to advance cross-project integration and synthesis; 78 participants attended. Maintained workshop website with workshop materials, presentations, agenda, and participant list (http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/2007_oct_sass/index.html).

Focused Science Planning Efforts—Over this Cooperative Agreement period, ARCUS has provided various levels of organizational support for the following focused ARCSS research efforts:

- Study of Northern Alaska Coastal System (SNACS) Support.*** In early 2004, NSF released an AO for SNACS. Lying at the intersection of the land, ocean, and atmosphere, and the locus of much human activity, the coast is a critical interface in the arctic system and an ideal test bed for tackling the kinds of complex scientific issues required to develop a true systems approach to the Arctic. The SNACS program solicitation drew on 2 science plans from the ARCSS research community: Land-Shelf Interactions and Pan-Arctic Cycles, Transitions, and Sustainability. NSF was able to fund 6 projects for a total of \$7.27 million in 2005 and 2006. ARCUS has supported this effort in several ways:
- Implemented a subcontract with the Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory to support a SNACS synthesis coordinator.
 - Developed, launched, and maintained a SNACS website providing information about the effort, individual research projects, and meetings and workshops: <http://www.arcus.org/arcss/snacs/>.
 - Assisted in coordination of SNACS teleconferences.
 - Assisted SNACS PIs and synthesis coordinator in planning and coordination of a March 2006 meeting in Seattle, WA, for SNACS investigators to discuss overarching themes and linkages between projects, approaches for synthesis, and future directions and activities; 49 participants attended. Maintained meeting website with meeting

materials, agenda, and participant list:

http://www.arcus.org/arcss/snacs/meetings/2006_seattle/index.php

- Ensured SNACS representation in relevant ARCSS meetings and activities.

Freshwater Integration Study (FWI) Support—In January 2001, NSF solicited proposals for the Freshwater Integration Study (FWI), with the goal of identifying, documenting, and understanding changes in arctic hydrological processes and their interactions with climate, ecosystem dynamics, and marine processes.

- In collaboration with the FWI science management office, in 2004 ARCUS reprinted and distributed 500 copies of *The Hydrologic Cycle and its Role in Arctic and Global Environmental Change: A Rationale and Strategy for Synthesis Study* due to continued communitywide demand for the publication, originally published in 2001 (see Activity 2.2.4).
- Ensured FWI representation in relevant ARCSS meetings and activities.

Shelf Basin Interactions (SBI)—The goal of the SBI project is to improve understanding of the impacts of global change on the physical and biogeochemical connections among the continental shelves, slopes, and deep basins of the western Arctic. SBI was designed through cooperative science planning to include three phases. Phase I (1999–2001) included retrospective synthesis, opportunistic sampling, and modeling; Phase II (2002–2006) was an ongoing multi-year field program and modeling effort in the Amerasian Arctic; and Phase III (2007–2009) aims to integrate and synthesize results of SBI Phase I and II with those of other projects into pan-arctic and global models in order to improve our understanding of the arctic system as a whole.

- ARCUS worked with the SBI Advisory Committee and Project Office to coordinate an eTown Meeting in January 2006, which provided an open forum to discuss implementation objectives and planning for SBI Phase III and solicited community input for a systems approach to understanding arctic shelf-basin dynamics; 28 participants attended.
- Worked with the AC to ensure that Phase III of SBI had system-wide relevance and contributed to overall synthesis efforts. The Announcement of Opportunity for Phase III was released in December 2006 (http://www.nsf.gov/publications/pub_summ.jsp?ods_key=nsf07532), and NSF funded 10 projects.

Seasonality in the Arctic System. Results from the ARCSS research community and others have clearly demonstrated that pervasive changes in the patterns of seasonality in the Arctic are underway. Recommendations from the ARCSS All-Hands Workshop in 2002 and subsequent community discussions, particularly those facilitated through the ARCSS Communities of Practice, identified changing seasonality as an interdisciplinary and cross-cutting science uncertainty that addresses a key unknown in our ability to predict arctic system behavior.

- Provided organizational support, including teleconference meetings, e-mail listserve services, and other communications, to the Near-Surfaces Processes Co-oP, chaired by Andrea Lloyd of Middlebury College. This Co-oP started in 2005 and worked with the AC and broader community to submit a prospectus focused on exploring how changing surface conditions (ice, snow, vegetation, infrastructure, human patterns of population) affect the linkages between arctic system components. The prospectus is

- available online at: http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/downloads/near-surface_processes_11_14_06.pdf.
- In December 2006, ARCUS helped organize a small writing group, which drafted an implementation plan entitled *Surface Transformations in the Arctic Environment (STATE)*. This document is available online at: <http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/cop.html>.
 - From planning and discussions at the October 2007 synthesis workshops, the topic of “seasonality,” which is included in the STATE prospectus, emerged as a key ARCSS priority. ARCUS worked with the ARCSS Committee to draft recommendations to NSF for a Seasonality research effort. A program solicitation titled Changing Seasonality in the Arctic System (CSAS) was released by NSF in June 2008 (http://www.nsf.gov/funding/pgm_summ.jsp?pims_id=503195), subsequent to this Cooperative Agreement period.

Development of ARCSS Data and Modeling Efforts—Community discussions on the importance of coherent and science-driven data management activities began at the 1996 ARCSS All-Hands Workshop. Subsequent discussions led to a 2003 internal report by the ARCSS Committee’s *ad hoc* ARCSS Data Working Group outlining recommendations for a revised ARCSS data management structure. As continued community discussions underscored the increasing need for data activities to serve the evolving requirements of ARCSS science, ARCUS worked with the AC and NSF Program Director to actively engage the research community in developing improved data and modeling approaches that address arctic system science and policy questions. Specific activities included:

March 2006 eTown Meeting—ARCUS worked with the AC to sponsor this online meeting, which provided an open forum for community input on data and modeling strategies for arctic system synthesis. This eTown Meeting focused on ways that data can be managed and disseminated to facilitate synthesis and dissemination of arctic system science. There were 34 meeting participants. Developed web pages with meeting materials and presentation (http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/ETM/march_06/data/).

December 2006 Town Hall Meeting—Planned and coordinated, in collaboration with the AC, a Town Hall meeting during the fall AGU meeting in San Francisco, CA, focusing on the emerging needs of ARCSS data management and recommendations for approaches to advance the ARCSS research agenda. Discussion focused on 3 fundamental topics: the scientific rationale for a new approach to ARCSS data management; identified priorities for data management that advances system-scale science; and ways in which the research community could plan strategically for the future of ARCSS Program data management. Developed web pages with meeting materials (http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/2006_Data_AGU/index.html).

March 2007 eTown Meeting—ARCUS coordinated this online meeting to discuss priorities and strategies for ARCSS data management for promoting arctic system-level understanding and synthesis. The meeting focused on the central discussion points to be considered during an April 2007 workshop: (1) What are the data and modeling needs to advance synthesis-focused arctic system science? (2) What is currently working, and what is needed in terms of applying data and modeling for analysis to advance science? What are the keys to success? (3) What are the practical steps forward as far as

mechanisms, approaches, tools and procedures, organization, standards, and related issues? There were 48 meeting participants. Developed web pages with meeting materials (http://www.arcus.org/arcss/etm/march_07/index.html).

April 2007 Workshop on New Perspectives through Data Discovery and Modeling—In April 2007, in collaboration with a workshop organizing committee, ARCUS planned, organized, convened, and staffed a workshop bringing together representatives of the data provider and data user communities to identify various ways that data and modeling strategies could be implemented to promote arctic system synthesis, improve scientific understanding and prediction, and increase the utility of scientific results to policymakers, educators, students, and the public. The 3-day workshop was attended by 58 in-person participants and over 20 online participants via webcasting. The workshop consisted of plenary talks and discussion, working groups, and poster sessions on the state-of-the art in data-modeling-synthesis fusion. Developed web pages with meeting materials (http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/2007_data/index.html).

A central recommendation that arose from the workshop was the creation of a new framework to foster data and model integration. This framework—***The Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory***—is envisioned as an “umbrella” concept that fosters interactions among arctic scientists and other stakeholders; integrated data analysis and modeling activities; outreach, education, and policy-relevant resources; and training and development of the arctic science community.

- ARCUS worked with the AC to draft a summary of the recommendations that emerged from the workshop, which was posted on the ARCSS website and distributed via relevant listserves (http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/message_050707.html).
- Organized an eTown meeting in December 2007, which sought community input for developing the Collaboratory. There were 28 participants (http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/etm/december_07/index.html).
- Coordinated a Town Hall meeting during the 2007 fall AGU Meeting to provide another venue for community input (http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/2007_data_agu/index.html).
- Developed and distributed informational material at relevant meetings and venues.

Outreach and Communication—In addition to the focused information-sharing activities described above, ARCUS disseminates information about overall ARCSS Program activities in an efficient and timely manner to a broad network of connections with individuals and institutions.

ARCSS Website—As the ARCSS Science Management Office, ARCUS developed, launched, maintained, and expanded a central ARCSS website providing information about the ARCSS Program, ARCSS research efforts, funding opportunities, synthesis efforts, community planning and surveys, meetings and workshops, ARCSS publications, and other related resources. The ARCSS website is available at: <http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/index.html>.

ARCSS Listserve—Developed, implemented, and moderated an ARCSS Listserve to broadcast announcements about research initiatives, funding opportunities, meetings, and

related activities focused on the ARCSS Program. The ARCSS Listserve currently has over 770 subscribers.

Other Information Distribution—ARCUS also provides general support for ARCSS science steering committees, science management offices, and researchers working on new initiatives, by preparing and distributing information, graphics, and publications about ARCSS Program research upon request.

2.2.2 ARCSS All-Hands Workshop 2002

With oversight from the NSF ARCSS Program Director and the ARCSS Committee, ARCUS planned, organized, convened, and staffed the ARCSS All-Hands Workshop, held in February 2002, in Seattle, WA. The workshop brought together 302 researchers, 87 of whom were students or post-docs, representing a wide array of natural, social, and physical sciences, to discuss the current state of knowledge about the arctic system and to look toward the future of arctic system research. The workshop provided an excellent forum for sharing research, exchanging ideas, and interacting with researchers from disparate disciplines.

- Worked with ARCSS Committee chair, committee members, and the ARCSS science management infrastructure to assess the progress made in the ARCSS Program in the previous 5 years, identify key gaps and research priorities, and formulate the agenda and topics for the workshop; prepared, distributed for invited review, and revised workshop agenda multiple times between May 2001 and February 2002.
- Prepared and posted background material and registration information for the workshop on the ARCUS website. Developed an online abstract submission process and database so that all submitted abstracts could be viewed online.
- Distributed a broad community invitation to the workshop, including a call for abstracts, via Arctic Info, other electronic lists, and the ARCUS website.
- Worked with the ARCSS Committee chair, the ARCSS science management infrastructure, and the NSF ARCSS Program Director to prepare a database of all projects funded by the ARCSS Program, categorized by the ARCSS thematic focus, to identify gaps between research priorities identified in ARCSS Program science plans and the research actually funded and producing results.
- Worked with ARCSS science management infrastructure and ARCSS researchers to develop a list of ARCSS graduate and undergraduate students. Provided travel scholarships for 87 students and post-docs to participate in the workshop; each presented a poster and contributed to a young investigators' working group report.
- Worked with the ARCSS science management infrastructure and ARCSS researchers to prepare materials about research initiatives in the planning stage and to host 5 online forums to engage the broader research community in discussions in the month prior to the workshop sessions, on:
 - Current ARCSS Research: Key Uncertainties and Next Steps;
 - The pan-Arctic Community-wide Hydrological Analysis and Monitoring Program (Arctic-CHAMP);
 - The Nearshore and Coastal Processes Initiative;
 - Modes of Variability in the Arctic System; and
 - Biophysical Feedbacks and Transitions in the Arctic Regional System.
- Refined the topics for breakout groups at the workshop and recruited facilitators for the groups.

- Posted final agenda, participant list, working group instructions, and other meeting information on the ARCUS website and distributed it to all registered participants via email in advance of the meeting.
- Coordinated all arrangements for the workshop venue and the necessary technical and logistic support.
- Coordinated travel and participant arrangements for the workshop. Paid travel for invited speakers, ARCSS Committee members, and students, and paid for other meeting and support costs associated with the workshop.
- Prepared a draft compilation of the 176 abstracts submitted prior to the workshop for distribution and review at the workshop.
- Provided staff support for the 4-day, 302-participant workshop. Participants represented 96 different institutions or organizations from 6 countries.
- Posted follow-up information on the ARCUS website after the workshop, including PDF and Powerpoint downloads of all the presentations, a PDF of the online forum discussions, and poster and presentation abstracts (<http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/allhands2002/index.html>).
- Worked with working group facilitators and presenters and the ARCSS Committee to synthesize recommendations from the workshop and make them available to the research community online for comment.
- Prepared, published, and distributed 1500 copies of *Proceedings of the ARCSS All-Hands Workshop 2002*. The proceedings include 11 oral presentation abstracts, 173 poster abstracts, a summary of the recommendations from each working group, and the ARCSS Committee's analysis and synthesis of recommendations for further planning and implementation of ARCSS Program priorities. A downloadable PDF of the publication is available on the ARCUS website (http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/allhands2002/AHW_Proceedings.html).

2.2.3 Coordinating a Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) Science Management Office

The HARC Core Office was established at ARCUS in August 2001 and was eventually subcontracted by ARCUS to the University of Alaska Fairbanks (UAF) Center for Global Change (CGC) starting 1 July 2004. For clarity and continuity, the activities undertaken through the UAF subcontract are reported below as HARC Core Office Activities, although the costs of these activities are included in the ARCSS Coordination budget.

The HARC Core Office works to build the HARC community's research capacity; synthesize HARC scientific knowledge; integrate this knowledge into larger ARCSS synthesis efforts; refine and communicate the HARC research vision; and sustain active involvement in ongoing ARCSS Program planning. The HARC Core Office director (Henry Huntington of Huntington Consulting, 2001–2004; Maribeth Murray of the University of Alaska Fairbanks, 2004–2008) also serves on the ARCSS Committee.

Core Office Activities 2001–2004

HARC Website—Developed, launched, maintained, and expanded a HARC website with background information and useful links and contacts (<http://www.arcus.org/harc/index.html>).

Focused Online Workshops—Planned and implemented a series of five online workshops focused on human dimensions aspects of specific arctic research topics in Fall 2001 (<http://www.arcus.org/harc/webshops.html>) and Spring 2002 (http://www.arcus.org/harc/webshops_02.html). Designed to engage the broader multi-disciplinary research community in discussions related to potential HARC research, each workshop examined a specific topic, including arctic hydrology, changing treeline, the arctic nearshore zone, changing weather patterns, and diminishing sea ice. Between 65 and 154 individuals registered for each workshop.

- Announced each workshop via ArcticInfo; sent specific invitations to individuals identified by their disciplinary and research interests in the Directory of Arctic Researchers. Prepared and provided background information about the HARC effort, biographical information about the workshop moderators, relevant reference materials, online registration, participant lists, and access to and instructions for the online workshops.
- Prepared daily summaries of online forum discussions, distributed them to registered participants, and posted summaries online each day of the workshop.
- Prepared final reports in PDF summarizing discussions and recommendations from each online workshop, distributed reports to all registered participants, and announced availability of reports to the broader research community via Arctic Info. All reports are also available for downloading from the HARC website.

Lessons in Integrated Analysis of Human Dimensions Research Workshop—

Organized and supported a Lessons in Integrated Analysis of Human Dimensions Research Workshop in May 2003. Although this small workshop was funded primarily through the NSF Biocomplexity in the Environment program, it received a small amount of staff support through the ARCUS Cooperative Agreement funds and contributed to the overall HARC development effort. Outcomes of this workshop included:

- A HARC synthesis paper (Huntington, et al. 2007. Understanding the human dimensions of the rapidly changing Arctic system: Insights and approaches from five HARC projects. *Regional Environmental Change* 7: 173–186).
- A report on HARC Core Office activities and plans for 2003–2004, which was submitted to the NSF ARCSS and Arctic Social Science program managers in June 2003. This report includes *Experiences in Synthesis*, a white paper prepared and offered to ARCSS Committee as a contribution to the ARCSS synthesis effort, and another white paper, *Suggestions for Improving the Preparation and Review of Interdisciplinary Proposals*.

Patterns, Connections, and Methods Workshop—Organized and supported a 2-day HARC Patterns, Connections, and Methods Workshop, held in Seattle, Washington in conjunction with the SEARCH Open Science Meeting in October 2003. This open workshop included presentations and posters from HARC PIs as well as others doing integrative human/environment interactions research both within and outside of the Arctic. The workshop drew 99 participants, including 22 students (both graduate and undergraduate). Several Alaska Native elders attended, as well as representatives from several Alaska State, Canadian, and U.S. federal agencies. ARCUS partnered with the Alaska Native Science Commission (ANSC) to entrain several Alaska Native students. Two ANSC commissioners attended as well.

- Recruited and convened a 10-member organizing committee representing diverse research disciplines and human dimensions expertise to plan the workshop, after which the committee continued to function as the HARC Science Steering Committee (SSC) to provide vision and guidance to the HARC program. The HARC SSC has been active via teleconference and face-to-face meetings.
- The workshop presentations, abstracts, and summaries of the discussions are available on the HARC website (<http://www.arcus.org/harc/pcm.html>).

Coupled Human and Natural Systems Workshop—Planned, organized, and convened a HARC/Biocomplexity in the Environment (BE): Coupled Human and Natural Systems Workshop in November 2002 (Anchorage, AK). Although funded separately from the Cooperative Agreement, this 42-person workshop contributed to the coordination of research and integration activities conducted by the HARC Core Office and funded through the ARCUS Cooperative Agreement with NSF. Participants in 8 interdisciplinary research teams examined HARC/BE questions and challenges toward submitting proposals on arctic human dimensions topics to future NSF BE program opportunities.

Special Issue of the Journal ARCTIC—Arranged for a HARC special issue of the journal *ARCTIC*, published in late 2004, containing 9 papers on a diverse array of human dimensions research topics. Also solicited contributions from funded HARC researchers; assisted in coordination and distribution of copies. The journal is available online (http://www.aina.ucalgary.ca/scripts/minisa.dll/144/proe/proarc/se+arctic,+v.+57,+no.++4,+Dec.+2004,*?COMMANDSEARCH).

Community Presentations—Supported information sharing by HARC leadership with the broader community, including assisting with preparation for presentations on HARC research and facilitating meetings of HARC principal investigators and other interested researchers at a variety of venues, including:

- The ARCSS All-Hands Workshop in Seattle, WA, February 2002.
- A HARC special session at the Arctic Workshop in Boulder, CO, in March 2002.
- A HARC workshop at the Center for Global Change and Arctic System research at the University of Alaska Fairbanks, in April 2002.

Core Office Activities 2004–2008

ARCUS worked with the new core office director Maribeth Murray of the University of Alaska Fairbanks to transfer the HARC office from ARCUS to the University of Alaska Fairbanks Center for Global Change (CGC) in 2004. ARCUS continued to collaborate with CGC on a variety of HARC planning and community development activities.

HARC Science Steering Committee (SSC) Support—Continued to work with the HARC SSC and the broader community to develop and update HARC-related priorities and activities.

- Planned, organized, and convened 4–6 SSC teleconferences each year and 2 in-person meetings since 2004 (see below).

- Supported the participation of HARC leadership in the ARCSS Near Surface Process Community of Practice planning process to ensure representation of the human dimensions perspective.
- Supported the participation of HARC leadership in organization and implementation of ARCSS planning meetings. Developed webpages with relevant meeting materials and information (http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/arcss_meetings.html).

Human Dimensions Research in the Context of IPY Community Meeting—In conjunction with the ARCUS Arctic Forum in Washington, D.C., in May 2007, planned, organized, and convened an open community meeting, Human Dimensions Research in the Context of IPY; 19 participants provided community input and feedback on planned International Polar Year (IPY) activities, including discussion on HARC Core Office activities over the past year and information about the current state of human dimensions research within the ARCSS Program and in the context of IPY. Members of the HARC SSC also met to discuss HARC activities. A summary of the meeting is available online (http://www.arcus.org/harc/dc_spring_07/meeting_summary.html).

HARC Synthesis Workshop—As part of a series of ARCSS meetings in Alexandria, VA, in October 2007, planned, organized, and convened a HARC Synthesis Workshop to foster synthesis-focused communication and interaction among Human Dimensions researchers in ARCSS and the Arctic Observing Network (AON); 36 participants discussed key issues, common challenges, and gaps in knowledge and developed recommendations for moving towards formal synthesis or new synthesis efforts. Members of the HARC SSC also met to discuss SSC business and planning priorities.

Human Dimensions Observing Network Brochure—With guidance from the HARC SSC, developed, published, and distributed a brochure titled *Designing the Human Dimension into an Arctic Observing Network*, which is available in hard copy and online (<http://www.arcus.org/harc/resources.html>).

HARC Special Sessions—Assisted Dr. Murray in organizing special sessions on HARC:

- Two sessions for the 6th *Open Meeting of the Human Dimensions of Global Environmental Change Research Community* in Bonn, Germany, October 2005. HARC sessions were co-chaired by Dr. Murray and Bruce Forbes, University of Lapland.
- A special session on the Contribution of Human Dimensions Research to Observing and Understanding the Current State of the Arctic at the *American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS) Arctic Science Conference* October 2006, Fairbanks, Alaska.

Community Presentations—Supported information sharing by HARC leadership, including assisting with preparation for presentations on HARC research and facilitating meetings of HARC investigators and other interested researchers at a variety of venues:

- Presented two HARC papers at the *Fifth International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences (ICASS V)* meeting in Fairbanks, Alaska, May 2004. Presentation is available online (<http://www.arcus.org/harc/resources.html>).

- Presented two HARC papers at the 55th *Arctic Science Conference, Human Dimensions of the Arctic Environment, American Association for the Advancement of Science* in Anchorage, Alaska, September 2004.
- Participated in the 12th *Annual Arctic Conference: Archaeology, Anthropology, and Environmental Studies* in Washington, D.C., November 2004.
- Presented HARC to CGC Steering Committee in Fairbanks, Alaska, September 2004.
- Participated in *Marine Science in Alaska: 2005 Symposium* in Anchorage, Alaska, January 2005.
- Participated in the *Alaska Forum on the Environment* in Anchorage, Alaska, February 2005, for the purpose of meeting with members of the Council of Athabascan Tribal Groups and the Alaska Native Science Commission.
- Participated in the *National Ecological Observing Network/High Latitude Ecological Observatory (NEON/HLEO) Open Meeting and Workshop* in Fairbanks, Alaska, February 2005.
- Presented a HARC paper at *Human Security and Climate Change International Workshop* in Oslo, Norway, June 2005.
- Presented HARC poster at the *American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS) Arctic Science Conference*, September 2005, in Kodiak, Alaska.
- Participated in the *Second International Conference on Arctic Research Planning (ICARP II)*, November 2005, in Copenhagen, Denmark.
- Presented an Overview of Human Dimensions Research at the ARCSS Committee Meeting, March 2006, in Seattle. Presentation is available online (<http://www.arcus.org/harc/resources.html>).
- Presented a HARC poster on Human Dimensions Research at the ARCSS Data Workshop in Seattle, April 2007. Poster is available online (<http://www.arcus.org/harc/resources.html>).
- Presented a HARC poster on Human Dimensions Research at the Arctic System Synthesis Workshop in Seattle, April 2007. Poster is available online (<http://www.arcus.org/harc/resources.html>).
- Served on the organizing committee for the Arctic Observation Integration workshops in Palisades, NY, March 2008, and presented on human dimensions integration and gaps in the Arctic Observing Network and human responses to the recent sea ice and climate system changes. Presentations are available online (<http://www.arcus.org/search/meetings/2008/aow/agendas.php>).
- Presented information on the human dimensions of arctic change at a May 2008 Congressional Briefing on Socioeconomic Tipping Points: Policy Implications of Arctic Climate Change in association with the ARCUS Arctic Forum. Presentation is available online (http://www.arcus.org/federal/2008_briefing.html).

2.2.4 Preparation and Publication of *CHAMP: The Hydrologic Cycle and its Role in Arctic and Global Environmental Change: A Rationale and Strategy for Synthesis Study*

Under a separate award to Charles Vörösmarty at the University of New Hampshire, the ARCSS Program supported a workshop on arctic hydrology in 2000; 33 participants identified gaps in

current understanding and developed a plan for future synthesis studies. ARCUS provided support for publishing the workshop report, including:

- Coordinated with workshop participants and co-chairs to outline report contents and draft sections of the report; edited text; obtained or created graphics and figures; prepared report layout; distributed to workshop participants for review; integrated review comments; prepared and circulated new draft for open community review; integrated community review comments; distributed report for final review by co-chairs and invited reviewers; integrated comments.
- Published and distributed 1,300 copies of the report (the University of New Hampshire paid printing costs with funds remaining from support for the initial planning workshop).
- Prepared a poster and a Powerpoint presentation summarizing the report's recommendations for use by the workshop co-chairs and other participants to provide information to the research community at scientific meetings.
- Compiled a set of extended abstracts from the workshop and made them available on the ARCUS website (http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/publications/hydro/white_papers.html).
- Reprinted the report by request (see section 2.2.1, Freshwater Integration Study [FWI] Support).
- Continued distribution of the report, including printed copies and electronically via a downloadable PDF on the ARCUS website (<http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/publications/hydro/index.html>).

The report defined 3 major research and synthesis challenges and provided recommendations for critical and strategic investments in arctic system science. NSF released an announcement of opportunity for these studies in 2002, and the resulting projects form the Freshwater Integration (FWI) Study, a component of the ARCSS Program that is currently in the synthesis phase. The FWI projects also represent an NSF contribution to two related programs: SEARCH (see section 1.4) and the international Arctic/Subarctic Ocean Fluxes (ASOF).

2.3 Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination

ARCUS has worked with the NSF Arctic Social Sciences Program Director to provide organizational support to the arctic social sciences research community, including convening a major international workshop and publishing two volumes of interest to the community.

2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Coordination and Planning

Arctic Social Sciences Workshop—In collaboration with the Alaska Native Science Commission (ANSC), ARCUS planned and convened a May 2004 workshop on Partnering with Arctic Communities, held as a 2-day special session at the Fifth International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences (ICASS-V) in Fairbanks, Alaska. The workshop highlighted the best practices in the field and demonstrated to young researchers how to conduct respectful, cooperative research in arctic and other communities. Approximately 70 people attended.

- In collaboration with the organizing committee, developed and revised the agenda; coordinated with ANSC and ICASS-V staff on workshop issues; facilitated travel and visa arrangements for presenters, many of them from Russia or rural Alaska; provided staff support; provided travel support for invited speakers and organizing committee

members; discussed the development of appropriate post-workshop products with the ANSC, the NSF Arctic Social Sciences Program Director, and the Partnering workshop participants. Workshop presentations are available on the ARCUS website (http://www.arcus.org/ASSP/2004_workshop.html).

- Supported a subcontract with the University of Alaska Fairbanks to provide staff support for the preliminary planning and coordination of ICASS V.

2.3.2 Translation and Publication of *Den Nye Sikkerhed - Groenland I Et Sikkerhedspolitisk Perspektiv (The New Security: Greenland in a Security Policy Perspective)*

Under the prior Cooperative Agreement with NSF, ARCUS coordinated initial planning for the English translation and publication of *Grønland i et Sikkerhedspolitisk Perspektiv (Greenland in a Security Policy Perspective)*, written by Jørgen Taagholt and Jens Claus Hansen. This study initially appeared in 1999 as part of the Danish Atlantic Treaty Association's series *Den Nye Sikkerhed (The New Security)*. The authors emphasized Greenland's role during the Cold War and the future security policy implications of Greenland. This book is an English translation of that study, and there have been modifications by the authors to this version.

- Edited translated text and prepared the book layout, including identifying and preparing appropriate graphics.
- Coordinated review of the draft by the co-authors, the translator, and several invited reviewers.
- Published 1,780 copies and presented the book at a March 2001 Security Political Seminar in Nuuk/Godthaab, Greenland.
- Continued distribution of *Grønland i et Sikkerhedspolitisk Perspektiv* at a number of political science or social sciences workshops and by request. The publication is also available electronically on the ARCUS website (<http://www.arcus.org/Publications/greenland/index.html>).

2.3.3 Preparation and Publication of *The Earth is Faster Now: Indigenous Observations of Arctic Environmental Change*

In cooperation with the Arctic Studies Center, Smithsonian Institution, in 2002 ARCUS published *The Earth is Faster Now: Indigenous Observations of Arctic Environmental Change*, a collection of 10 papers describing contemporary efforts to document indigenous knowledge of environmental change in the Arctic. Compiled and edited by Igor Krupnik of the Smithsonian Institution and Dyanna Jolly of Lincoln University, the volume reviews recent major individual studies on indigenous knowledge and climate change, primarily in North America. The text is accompanied by local and personal observations, quotations from interviews, illustrations, and photographs. Contributors include well-known academic researchers and Native people from Canada, Finland, and the United States. The publication is designed to be useful to both researchers and communities as a tool for networking and communication.

- Worked with the editors to determine the probable size of the volume, number of papers to be contributed, publication timeline, illustrations and graphics, and general layout requirements; received papers, including illustrations; coordinated review and revision process; completed editing and design of the publication.

- Published 1,500 copies of *The Earth is Faster Now* in time for a book launch and signing reception at the Canadian Embassy in Washington, D.C., in May 2002; distributed copies to member representatives and other attendees at the ARCUS 14th Annual Meeting. Smithsonian Institution funded printing of an additional 300 copies.
- Prepared a poster about the book for display at the ARCUS 14th and 15th Annual Meetings and *Arctic Forum*, at the 2002 and 2003 AAAS Arctic Science Conferences, at the 2002 AGU Fall Meeting, at the 7th Polar Meteorology conference in Hyannis, Massachusetts in May 2003, and at other venues.
- Developed a purchasing process including an order form, also available online (<http://www.arcus.org/store/#Publications>), and procedures for receiving and fulfilling orders. Sold copies of the book at a variety of arctic meetings and workshops, including the ARCUS 16th Annual Meeting and Arctic Forum and at the Alaska Math and Science Educators Conference. Held a book signing and reception at the Fifth International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences in May 2004. Distributed approximately 350 complimentary copies to book reviewers, chapter authors, and others. In 2004, commissioned a second printing using proceeds from the book's sales.

2.3.4 Humans in the Bering Sea Ecosystem Community Planning

In 2003, a group representing arctic social scientists and resident communities of the Bering Sea initiated a community planning process to develop a social science research plan for the Bering Sea to complement the Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) science plan (see section 1.5) and to capitalize on interest in collaborations among resident communities and natural and social scientists. ARCUS was asked by the NSF Arctic Social Sciences Program Manager to coordinate a community planning process to develop a social science research plan for the Bering Sea in order to establish responsible community-centered Bering Sea ecosystem research and partnerships between communities and researchers.

Community Guidance—ARCUS supported several activities to gather community input for this planning process:

- Worked with a 3-member steering committee and the NSF Arctic Social Sciences Program Manager to convene the Bering Sea Ecosystem Community Forum in Anchorage, Alaska, in March 2004. The goal of the Community Forum was to: explore community research interests, plan ways to collect a broader range of community priorities, and discuss the possible scope of the research plan. Arranged meeting logistics, participant materials, and staffed the 27-person workshop; participants included local residents, elders, representatives of native and local natural resource associations, social scientists, and other representatives of programs and projects centered on Bering Sea ecosystem.
- Worked with the steering committee to organize and convene the Humans and the Bering Ecosystem Town Meeting held during the Fifth International Congress of Arctic Social Scientists (ICASS V) in May 2004; 24 participants attended.
- Organized, convened, provided travel support, and staffed the Humans in the Bering Ecosystem Community Liaison Meeting in February 2006, in Anchorage, Alaska. 23 participants provided comments on a draft version of *Sustaining the Bering Ecosystem*:

A Social Sciences Research Plan and discussed broad concerns about community involvement in Bering Sea research and interactions between scientists and communities.

- Supported and coordinated the participation of social scientists in the BEST science steering committee and their contributions to the 2005 integrated BEST implementation plan (see section 1.5).
- Continued support and coordination for the BEST science advisory group to work with Bering Sea communities to gather and integrate community recommendations into the BEST program.

Science Plan Development—Provided support to the science advisory group to draft *Sustaining the Bering Ecosystem: A Social Sciences Research Plan*. Developed a section of the ARCUS website to support this development process. Notified the community of opportunities to review the draft report; distributed hard copies of drafts to Bering Sea communities for review; coordinated response to review comments. Following extensive review and revision, developed final draft of *Sustaining the Bering Ecosystem*, currently available as a PDF download on the ARCUS website; it is awaiting publication (<http://www.arcus.org/Bering/reports/index.html>).

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

ARCUS' education programs are developed around guiding principles that have been formulated over the past 12 years through several community workshops and our work with researchers, educators, students, and residents of the Arctic. These principles are:

- Education programs must be relevant, inquiry-based, and, if focused on K–12, they should align with National Science Education Standards.
- Education programs should build on existing education efforts; the community should focus on increased collaborations between established programs and networks and should build supportive partnerships between researchers, educators and schools, and communities.
- Arctic residents must be involved in developing and implementing educational programs and outreach, and effective partnerships should be promoted and nurtured.
- There is a need for increased awareness or “visibility” of the arctic region, its residents, the unique and analogous aspects of the Arctic as a polar region, and its role in the Earth system.

All ARCUS education programs fit into this context and are developed to:

- Ensure that high-quality information and education in arctic science is available to the general public, students, teachers, and Natives of the Arctic.
- Enable interested and talented students to pursue scientific careers in the Arctic.
- Ensure that the scientific and technical workforce exists to meet the challenges of the arctic research agenda.

3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities

Activities under this task can be generally described as providing organizational support to specific education projects funded by a variety of sources. This support promotes the development and successful implementation of arctic science education projects by sharing information and expertise, supporting communicative networks, and distributing information about results and opportunities. Specific activities included:

Eider Journey—Participated in a collaborative arctic science education project, *Eider Journey*, which provides research experiences for arctic students and teachers, in collaboration with several federal agencies and arctic communities. This interdisciplinary and multi-agency collaboration included the Alaska North Slope Borough (NSB) Department of Wildlife Management (DWM), the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS), Izembek Refuge, schools in Cold Bay, Alaska, the NSB School District, and faculty from the University of Alaska Fairbanks, along with ARCUS.

Eider Journey encouraged students, teachers, and community members to understand their local environment and provided a basis of knowledge from which they can make informed decisions. The project engaged students and teachers in scientific research and provided training on field methods, analysis, and hypothesis testing. Activities initiated and supported by ARCUS included coordination of teacher and student participation with the research project, assistance in the development of educational materials, and use of distance-delivery education resources through Arctic Alive! (see section 3.4). The collaborative work on *Eider Journey* also made possible funding from the National Fish and Wildlife Foundation to develop an educator's guide to support this and other arctic science education projects.

Shaping Vocational Frontiers—Provided scientific and educational contacts for *Shaping Vocational Frontiers: Science, Engineering and Mathematics for Persons with Disabilities in Rural and Remote Areas*, a project conducted by the University of Hawaii and Access Alaska and funded by NSF Education and Human Resources (EHR).

Rural Systemic Initiative—Worked with the Alaska Federation of Natives (AFN), the Alaska Native Knowledge Network (ANKN), and the University of Alaska Fairbanks in collaboration with the NSF-funded Rural Systemic Initiative (RSI), to compile integrated curricular materials and to make them available to a wide national audience and to provide technical assistance and training to RSI participants in Alaskan communities.

Communicating with Northern Communities—Continued working with Arctic Native organizations and scientists to develop effective means by which the results of NSF-funded research can be returned to northern communities. ARCUS continues to develop relationships, resources, and expertise in this area. One example of planning at this level was ARCUS staff participation in the Education Working Group at the April 2001 Barrow facilities planning workshop in Barrow, Alaska.

Frozen Worlds—Provided information and recommendations to the National Geographic Society's JASON Project IV—Frozen Worlds. Recommended and helped facilitate contact with NSF-funded investigators to work with and provide information to teachers about the Arctic.

Education Insert—Prepared a 4-page insert to *Witness the Arctic* providing information and advice to researchers on developing appropriate and useful science education projects, including information about education on global climate change, indigenous knowledge, and tips on bringing research into the classroom.

Information Sharing—Presented information about science education projects and opportunities at research community seminars, such as the University of Alaska Center for Global Change information series, and at scientific meetings, such as the American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS) annual Arctic Science Conference, the American Geophysical Union (AGU) annual fall meeting, and at others as opportunities arose.

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

ARCUS implemented an Arctic Visiting Speakers' (AVS) Series in January 2000 to increase communication and collaboration among the dispersed arctic research community and to nurture understanding and communication between arctic researchers and communities. The Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series funded researchers and other arctic experts to travel and share their knowledge in communities where they might not otherwise connect. Speakers covered a wide range of arctic research topics and addressed a variety of audiences including K–12 students, graduate and undergraduate students, and the public.

The Series supported travel costs for 58 speaking tours from 2001–2008, addressing arctic issues at 193 different public engagements. Speakers presented at a variety of public venues including museums, schools, workshops, science fairs, and graduate seminars. A number of speakers held multi-day workshops for the public and conducted various media interviews (i.e., newspaper and radio). An estimated 6200 people attended the public presentations. Information about every tour is available on the ARCUS website (http://www.arcus.org/arctic_speaker/index.html):

- Of the 58 speaking tours, 25 speakers traveled either from other countries to speak in the U.S. or from the U.S. to other countries. The remaining 33 U.S. speakers visited institutions within the U.S.
- Topics covered included: Native land claim issues, self-governance and capitalism, Inuit culture and indigenous law, Eskimo whaling and a changing arctic environment, hydrochemistry, eco-hydraulics, Karelian folk culture, and many others.
- ARCUS maintains a Speaker's Bureau—an online directory of arctic researchers and experts who are available to visit organizations, communities or schools to give presentations. The Bureau currently has 65 profiles for potential Arctic Visiting Speakers. Institutions looking for a speaker to invite can use the bureau as a resource but may also invite a speaker who is not a member of the bureau.
- Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series brochures were distributed at various conferences.

3.3 Arctic Science Education Report

Under the previous Cooperative Agreement, ARCUS convened a 15-member working group of selected researchers, educators, students, and arctic community representatives in March 2000, to review various programs and educational approaches to science education and to prepare recommendations for the development of research-experience-based science education programs for the Arctic. The previous agreement also supported development of the report and circulation of the draft for community review.

Under the current award, ARCUS staff completed editing and layout, published the report, titled *Arctic Science Education: Recommendations from the Working Group on Arctic Science Education to the National Science Foundation*, distributed 600 printed copies, and made the report and its recommendations available electronically through the ARCUS website (<http://www.arcus.org/Publications/index.html>). All available copies have been distributed, but we continue to receive many inquiries for this report and distribute Xeroxed copies upon request.

3.4 Arctic Alive!

In September 2001, ARCUS was awarded funding through the NSF Directorate for Geosciences to develop and implement a pilot distance-delivery education program. Arctic Alive! allowed students to participate in arctic research without leaving their classrooms. This program was based on a very successful program called LEARNZ developed by Heurisko Ltd. in New Zealand. The second year (2003–2004) of Arctic Alive! was partially funded through the Cooperative Agreement.

Five classrooms (grades 6–9) and 3 home school families from across Alaska participated in the pilot April 2002 “virtual field trip” located outside of Barrow, Alaska. This first “virtual field trip” focused on geoscience research and examined the arctic climate, sea ice, and climate change. Over the course of 5 days, students learned about albedo transect research, ice core

research, and ice core data analysis from researchers and heard from Barrow community members about their perspective on climate change. To support student participation, ARCUS developed:

- A comprehensive website that included secure areas for teachers and students to access all materials and resources; complete on-line lesson plans that could be used individually or as a unit and that meet Alaska state and national content standards in science, technology, and math; an on-line discussion forum where students and researchers could interact; and downloadable Word and PDF files of all the materials.
- Free access to daily audio-conference calls where students and researchers were able to interact in real time; online curriculum materials and audio files are available to classrooms that were unable to participate in the virtual field trip in real-time.

Teachers and students evaluated the project following the completion of the field trip and classroom activities; in addition, Cindy Fabbri, who participated in the program as a curriculum developer, studied the program's outcomes for her Master's thesis. Evaluations were positive and encouraged continued development of the program. An Arctic Alive! brochure was created and widely distributed at a number of arctic conferences and workshops as well as at several national science education conferences.

Three Arctic Alive! field expeditions were implemented in 2003:

2003 Ecological Change Expedition: This expedition focused on ecological change in Kotzebue Sound. The research used Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) and Scientific Ecological Knowledge (SEK) to develop an ecological profile of the nearshore benthic ecosystem in Kotzebue Sound.

2003 Snow Science: Researcher Merrick Johnston and team skied 400 miles through Northwest Alaska. Merrick's research objective was to determine how storm tracks affect contaminant loading in Northwest Alaska and to evaluate how this may vary with inter-annual weather patterns. With assistance from local students, members of the research team dug snow pits, collected snow samples, and interviewed Elders along the way. Merrick posted journal entries, photos, and responded to student questions as she traveled from village to village.

2003–2004 Eider Journey: See section 3.1 for background on *Eider Journey*. With support from Arctic Alive!, high school students from Barrow, Alaska, worked with biologists in both the eiders' nesting areas near Barrow and at their wintering areas near Cold Bay to develop an increased understanding of the needs of this species and the threats it faces.

Elements of Arctic Alive! have been incorporated into the Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating (TREC) program (see Section 3.5. below). Arctic Alive! materials are archived at the Digital Library for Earth Science Education (DLESE; <http://www.dlese.org:80/library/>).

3.5 Teachers and Researchers - Exploring and Collaborating (TREC)

The Teachers and Researchers - Exploring and Collaborating (TREC) program was an educational research experience in which K–12 teachers participated in arctic research, working closely with scientists as a pathway to improving science education through teachers'

experiences in scientific inquiry. TREC built on the outstanding scientific and cultural opportunities of the Arctic to link research and education through intriguing topics that engaged students and the wider public. All TREC activities and resources were made available through the TREC website (<http://www.arcus.org/trec/index.php>). Beginning in 2007, NSF provided funding through a separate award to support a similar education program in both polar regions known as PolarTREC (<http://www.polar-trec.com/home>).

TREC activities began in January 2004 and continued through December 2006. ARCUS coordinated and supported a total of 27 teacher and research projects (TREC teams) for the 2004–2006 field seasons. The main components and activities of TREC included:

Arctic Field Research Experience—The core of the TREC program was the field research experience, whereby TREC teachers participate in arctic field research for two or more weeks during spring/summer. Selected research projects represented the leading edge of scientific inquiry and included the K–12 teacher as an integral part of the science team.

- Convened a management group in partnership with VECO Polar Resources and worked with the management group to determine scope of program, program planning components, task scheduling, and coordinate logistical support for each TREC teacher.
- Developed program materials, including program description, expectations, and participation requirements for teachers and researchers, online seminar and website materials, and press materials to communicate TREC projects to public media outlets. Organized and convened preliminary webinars (online seminars) to provide interested researchers more information about TREC program opportunities; announced program via ArcticInfo, ARCUS website, and education listserves.
- Developed, launched, and maintained TREC website, which includes program information, participation requirements, online application process, weblinks, and structure for program participants to interact online. The TREC website supports teacher and researcher interactions, online interactive journaling and photo albums, information about the TREC research projects, and the development of the TREC learning resources database.
- Designed and implemented application process for teachers and researchers for each field season; 106 teachers applied to the program; convened selection committee to select and match teachers and researchers from applicant pool.
- Planned and convened annual in-person orientation workshops for TREC teachers, including safety training, technology training, and discussion and planning regarding classroom and outreach activities. Coordinated and supported TREC teacher deployment to the field.

Classroom and Public Connections—Teachers and researchers connected with classrooms and the public through use of Internet tools such as online teacher and researcher journals, message boards, photo albums, real-time presentations and calls from the field, and online learning resources.

- Developed and refined tools to facilitate the online collaboration between teachers, researchers, and the community, including webinars (real-time seminars broadcast over the Internet), bulletin board forums, chat capabilities, file sharing workspace, on-line

calendar and field journals.

- Developed content for and conducted orientation and post-field webinars for participating teachers and researchers.
- Coordinated and supported TREC team interactions and planning for the pre- and post-field portions of the TREC experience. Coordinated and supported TREC teachers' ongoing (including in-field) communications with other educators, students and classrooms, and the public. Implemented Virtual Campfire Chats as TREC teachers and researchers returned from their field research experiences. The Virtual Campfire Chats were public internet-seminars led by arctic researchers and educators on various topics of arctic research.

Professional Development—TREC provided professional development opportunities for teachers who participated in field research projects as well as educators who connected through the Internet. TREC provided a variety of content, tools, and seminars geared toward subject matter learning, teaching practices, and alignment of TREC experiences with professional and teaching standards.

- Worked with Teachers Experiencing Antarctica and the Arctic (TEA) staff to develop case study evaluations of TREC teachers to determine the success of the field research experience for positively affecting science teaching and learning in the classroom. Ute Kaden, a 2005 TREC teacher, evaluated TREC for her Ed.D. dissertation from the University of Houston, concluding that TREC was an effective professional development program in refining science teachers' knowledge, skills, and confidence to teach science effectively, renewing their enthusiasm for teaching, and promoting student learning.
- Coordinated and supported teacher and research project interactions and planning prior to and following the field portion of the TREC experience.
- Implemented a formative evaluation process to gather information about the application process, selection, accessibility, content, ease of use, involvement of underserved populations, and outreach to arctic residents.

Sustained Community and Support—The TREC program was designed to extend the experience beyond field research to support a sustained community of teachers, scientists, and the public through online seminars, an e-mail listserv, and teacher-to-teacher peer groups.

- Convened support groups for teachers, called Connecting Arctic/Antarctic Researchers and Educators (CARE), in collaboration with TEA staff, to provide a means by which science educators who have participated in research experiences can discuss relevant issues, such as classroom and pedagogical practices, professional development, integrating field research into the classroom, and curriculum development.
- Implemented the Arctic Science Education Listserv to communicate arctic science education activities and opportunities to a broad audience.
- Organized and convened the Arctic Learning Symposium at the conclusion of each year—a virtual conference where TREC teachers and researchers shared what they learned from the experience, worked together to integrate learning resources and curriculum materials developed during the year, and provided information to potential TREC participants and any individuals interested in using information developed through the TREC program.

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

ARCUS has used a variety of information and outreach methods to disseminate timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, and the public. These methods include a newsletter, the ARCUS website, email listserves, online directories and archives, and several other projects. Specific activities included:

4.1 *Witness the Arctic: Chronicles of the NSF Arctic Sciences Program*

Witness the Arctic is a newsletter, available online and in hardcopy, that provides information on current arctic research and education efforts and news, significant research initiatives, national policy affecting arctic science, research support and logistics, profiles of institutions with major arctic research efforts, and calendar events and publications. With edited contributions from representatives throughout the arctic research and education community, *Witness the Arctic* is a substantive and significant source of information.

Between July 2001 and March 2008, ARCUS published and distributed 7 issues of *Witness the Arctic*, each between 28 and 32 pages long and including special 4–6 page inserts. Feature stories have included an overview of the 2004 Arctic Climate Impact Assessment (ACIA), the history of the previous International Polar Years, and an update on projects integrating arctic research and education.

- *Witness the Arctic* currently has over 13,700 subscribers, up from fewer than 7,000 in 2001. Of these subscribers, 5,200 are outside the U.S.
- Each issue contains material from approximately 50 contributors, including academic researchers, program managers, agency personnel, educators, and facility managers, both U.S. and international.
- The number of newsletter subscribers continues to increase with each issue, with commensurate increases in distribution costs. ARCUS implemented a new distribution method for international subscribers in 2002, which significantly reduced mailing costs.

4.2 Website/Internet Resources

The ARCUS website provides essential information and resources for the diverse and geographically distributed arctic research community and serves over 6,000 files from over 2,000 pages. The website is the focal point for web-served educational programs such as PolarTREC, various community science planning efforts, and provides important information and resources to the research community about research programs, meetings, community activities, and publications. Among many other resources, the website provides program information, electronic copies of publications, agenda, abstracts, and participant lists from arctic meetings, and audio and video archives from a variety of programs and meetings.

In addition to content development for a variety of programs and activities, many improvements to the website structure and function have been made since 2001. Users benefit from ease of use through a more intuitive interface and vastly decreased page-load times due to these changes. The ARCUS website increasingly utilizes user-driven or user-created content. This transition has been coincident with and prompted by changes in browser technology as well as standard practices of many leading websites on the World Wide Web. Data and information are dynamically served from external 4D and MySQL databases, and the site features dynamic,

user-created content through simple interfaces such as message boards and forums, photo albums, and calendars. Specific improvements include:

- Redesigned or added major sections of the website to provide program information and to improve search functions, information delivery, and ease of information management. Website improvements for specific projects are discussed in the relevant project activity descriptions in this report.
- Improved file structure and site architecture for major sections of the website; developed additional style sheets for improved consistency in visual layout; implemented new technology and software for improved security and user functionality; continued to improve accessibility standards and code-compliance throughout the website.
- Transitioned the online Calendar maintained by ARCUS to a collaborative Arctic Calendar, working jointly with the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) and the Arctic Ocean Sciences Board (AOSB); developed an online calendar event submission process, with an underlying database that can be accessed and managed by any of the collaborating organizations.

4.3 ArcticInfo Listserve

Since September 1996, ARCUS has maintained ArcticInfo, a moderated, broadcast only email list that provides the arctic science community with timely information about funding opportunities, important events, publications, position announcements, and other useful news. Information is submitted by community members, fact-checked, edited, formatted to stringent standards for clarity, and distributed to subscribers by email. The listserv has 6002 current subscribers, an increase of 2805 since 2001. Over the Cooperative Agreement period, ARCUS:

- Received, reviewed, and accepted or declined over 3000 submissions to ArcticInfo.
- Fact-checked, edited, formatted, and distributed 2722 announcements. On average, over 33 announcements were posted per month.
- Communicated with subscribers regarding announcements, special information requests, manual subscribe or unsubscribe requests, and other concerns.
- Maintained a searchable, online archive of all announcements posted.
- Maintained a database to track subscription activity.
- Attended to the bounce list by researching bounced announcements to correct and update addresses, investigating apparently dead domains, and deleting addresses that consistently bounced back from the subscriber list.
- Performed software maintenance and upgrade, allowing for a far more efficient distribution process, management of current subscribers, and maintenance of the subscriber list itself.
- There have been 3539 announcements distributed from ArcticInfo since its creation in September 1996. Each year has seen an increase in submissions for distribution and in subscribers.
- In addition to managing ArcticInfo, ARCUS has created and manages 17 additional electronic lists for the arctic research community. These lists range from small group lists for community planning groups or science steering committees to large community of researcher lists, similar to but less comprehensive than ArcticInfo. Some of the lists are participatory, meaning that any subscribed participant can post to the lists, and some are broadcast only, meaning that only designated people can post content to the lists.

4.4 The Directory of Arctic Researchers

Developed after extensive surveys of individual arctic researchers and institutions, the online Directory of Arctic Researchers was initiated in 1994 and is intended to aid links among individual investigators, institutions, funding agencies, and arctic stakeholders, thereby facilitating arctic research and education efforts. Directory entries include complete contact information, science specialties, current arctic research interests, and information about specific projects, areas of expertise, and collaborations. Entries are not posted in the directory until information is received directly from the researcher and evaluated and approved for inclusion by the compilers. Each researcher is requested to look over their entry and submit changes annually. Changes are accepted at any time, and the directory is updated.

- Added 820 new records in this reporting period. As of March 2008, there were a total of 4120 individual records in the Directory. Surveyed researchers with current directory records to get updated contact and current research information.
- Surveyed significant international research organizations and individuals to expand non-U.S. researcher records in the database.
- Maintained and regularly updated a downloadable PDF of the Directory including alphabetically listed individual researcher entries and a cross-reference file listing researchers by name within science specialty categories. Developed a new Directory PDF design and creation process, which streamlined the PDF creation and produces a smaller document and file size.
- Developed a customized PDF creation option, which allows users to easily create a customized PDF of their Directory search returns.
- Developed an automated daily Directory upload to the website and automated the daily PDF creation and upload of PDF files to the website.

4.5 Internet Graphics Archive (Internet Media Archive)

The ARCUS Internet Media Archive (IMA) is a collection of photos, graphics, videos, and presentations that have been collected for various purposes and shared through the Internet. The archive currently contains over 6500 photos, 450 videos, 270 audio files, 100 graphics and logos, and 28 presentations; approximately 13,000 files currently await processing before entering the archive. The contents of the archive are organized by the submitting photographer's name, by event, or by organization. All of the media available in the archive are accompanied by information about the content, the contributor or source, and usage requirements. Resources in the archive have been viewed 116,038 times.

- Set up a dedicated server for the storage and distribution of all resources contained in the Internet Media Archive.
- Evaluated and tested a variety of potential database software packages for the archive. The selected software includes a powerful search function by keyword, allows for easy categorization, access, and downloading, allows multiple types of media to be posted (photos, graphics, video), allows different levels of administrative access, and uses a point and click search feature.
- Organized and categorized resources by submitter/photographer. Developed and implemented a process to gather standardized and organized information about the resources to be posted into the archive; developed a legal permissions document to grant ARCUS

permission to post these resources on the Internet. The permissions document allows the photographer to grant varying levels of authorization for reproduction:

- Free with no restrictions or other requirements;
 - Free, but proper credit or attribution is required;
 - Free, but the creator must be notified about the use;
 - Free, but no modifications are allowed without permission.
 - A per-use fee is required; contact the creator to arrange for use and payment.
- Posted all photos and the majority of other media for which permission has been received to the online archive, with detailed information, use criteria, and keywords for the search interface. Developed and implemented a watermark logo approved by the photographers to prevent the unauthorized use of certain photos.
 - Finalized the public interface and tools, announced the resource via ArcticInfo, and made the Internet Media Archive available to the research community through the ARCUS website.

4.6 Arctic Community Outreach

ARCUS conducts a number of outreach activities that disseminate timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, educators and the public, and that build supportive networks among those groups to advance international arctic research efforts and our understanding of the Arctic.

Arctic Forum—Planned and hosted the annual *Arctic Forum* in conjunction with the ARCUS Annual Meeting in the Washington, D.C., area each spring. Participants at the *Arctic Forum* include arctic researchers from the U.S. and other countries, policy makers, federal agency personnel, educators, students, and arctic residents (http://www.arcus.org/annual_meetings/index.html).

- Each *Arctic Forum* agenda featured a mix of oral presentations, posters, keynote addresses, and panel discussions. Keynote speakers have included the directors of NSF and the U.S. Climate Change Science Program, a Native Elder from Barrow, Alaska, and the Swedish Ambassador to the U.S.
- Information was presented on research funded by NSF, arctic research supported by other federal agencies or programs, and significant international arctic research and education efforts.
- Beginning in 2005, each *Arctic Forum* has been web cast; participants viewing the Forum via the web cast were able to email questions and comments for the presenters to the co-chairs and ARCUS staff for inclusion in session discussions. An archive of the video footage is available online through each meeting's website and the Internet Media Archive.
- Abstracts from each *Arctic Forum* are compiled and published in an annual volume and distributed to participants and on request.
- Themes, chairs, and number of participants of the 2001–2007 *Arctic Forum*:
 - 2001. Interactions between the Biological and Physical Systems of the Arctic, chaired by John Hobbie of the Marine Biological Laboratory. 107 participants.
 - 2002. Biocomplexity in the Arctic, chaired by Sue Moore of the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. 90 participants.
 - 2003. Responding to Global Change: Resilience and Vulnerability in the Arctic System, co-chaired by Igor Krupnik of the Smithsonian Institution and F. Stuart Chapin of the University of Alaska Fairbanks. 121 participants.

2004. Recent Decrease of the Arctic Sea Ice: Its Causes, Consequences, and Historical Perspective, co-chaired by Wieslaw Maslowski of the Naval Postgraduate School and Mark Serreze of the University of Colorado Boulder. 112 participants.
2005. Arctic Climate Change and Public Literacy: What's at Stake? Co-chaired by Stephanie Pfirman of Barnard College and Bruce Forbes of the University of Lapland. 167 participants.
2006. International Arctic Research at a Turning Point: Innovations and Collaborations for the Future, co-chaired by Craig Tweedie of the University of Texas El Paso and Volker Rachold of the International Arctic Science Committee. 136 participants.
2007. Water in the Arctic: International Collaborations and Understanding Environmental Change, co-chaired by Larry Hinzman of the University of Alaska Fairbanks and Gunhild Rosqvist of Stockholm University. 136 participants.

Other Community Outreach

- Developed information resources regarding arctic research activities, needs, and priorities and participated in outreach activities at scientific meetings and workshops to inform the broader scientific community and key policy and decision-makers about important arctic research efforts and findings.
- Participated in or sponsored arctic outreach activities at relevant meetings and workshops, including the American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS) annual Arctic Science Conference, the American Geophysical Union (AGU) annual Fall Meeting, and at others as opportunities arose.

4.7 Publication: *The Arctic*

A need has long existed for a publication that introduces the environments and peoples of the Arctic and is scientifically accurate while remaining comprehensible and relevant to the general public, including middle and high school students. To address this need, ARCUS began developing an overview of the arctic region for a general audience in 2000, with funding through the previous Cooperative Agreement with NSF. Tentatively titled *The Arctic: Changes in a Polar Region*, this book is similar to a magazine in the quality of graphics and level of complexity and will be accessible to a wide range of readers. The contents and the publication design and layout are targeted to the general public and middle and high school students. The contents cover ocean, terrestrial, and human components of the Arctic and review various aspects of these domains, including contemporary and historical research, through a seasonal framework. Links among important arctic processes and between the biophysical systems and human cultures are illustrated. In early 2001, an invited group of educators, students, arctic researchers, and experts in science information development reviewed the draft publication. The reviews provided guidance for substantial revisions. Work on this publication was halted, after discussion and agreement with the NSF Program Officer, due to the high demand for staff resources to be dedicated to other more urgently needed projects.

4.8 Eider Endangered Species Consultation Bulletin

At the request of NSF, developed a draft consultation bulletin informing arctic researchers about the two species of sea duck that may be affected by activities associated with scientific research on the North Slope of Alaska, the spectacled eider (*Somateria fischeri*) and Steller's eider (*Polysticta stelleri*).

- Met with U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) staff to discuss the requirements for consultation with USFWS regarding potential impacts of research on listed species and to gather information about the consultation process. Researched the Endangered Species Act and the requirement that federal agencies consult with USFWS.
- Compiled background materials on the species, the critical time periods, and geographic areas of concern, including maps and photos. Designed a questionnaire to guide researchers and NSF program managers through a decision-making process to determine what level of consultation is required, how to initiate the consultation process, and who to contact for further information.
- Developed layout and contents of draft bulletin. The draft consultation bulletin was reviewed and approved by USFWS staff in the Endangered Species Division and sent to the Alaska North Slope Borough Department of Wildlife Management and the Barrow Arctic Science Consortium for review and comment. Revisions were made to the bulletin in accordance with the review comments. The draft consultation bulletin was forwarded to NSF Arctic Sciences Section for completion.

5. CORE SUPPORT

Core support provides management and infrastructure crucial to support the overall tasks and the projects and activities included in each task of the Cooperative Agreement. This category was initiated to ensure stability and continuity of the direct activities that support the whole of the Cooperative Agreement so they are not vulnerable to the changes in the specific tasks and activities funded from year-to-year through the agreement.

ARCUS is a relatively small non-profit organization, and the Executive Director is intimately involved in all activities of the organization including planning, prioritizing, managing, and directly implementing the work undertaken on behalf of the National Science Foundation. The Executive Director works closely with ARCUS project managers to prioritize tasks with respect to annual and longer-term plans and to manage individual workloads and projects. She closely reviews activities and products and ensures that projects are completed as scheduled and in accordance with the annual plan and that the products or effects of the activities are beneficial to arctic research and to the goals of the particular task funded through the Cooperative Agreement. She is directly involved in working with outside committees and contributors to ensure that projects are concluded effectively and in a timely fashion. The Executive Director also works closely with the ARCUS Business Manager in budgeting and reviewing ongoing project expenditures against the NSF budget. The Executive Director liaises directly with NSF on all planning, programmatic, and budget issues. This component of management is essential to the ongoing work ARCUS carries out on behalf of NSF.

Similarly, the Systems Administrator manages the network, server, and all technical needs required to support NSF tasks and project activities. He works directly with the Executive Director to ensure that all hardware and software requirements are met so that server and network operations supporting NSF activities are carried out smoothly and efficiently. The Executive Director and Systems Administrator plan for upcoming needs, including scientific meetings and conferences convened by ARCUS on behalf of the NSF, in conjunction with the annual program plan.

While the work of both these positions is directly related to the successful implementation of direct project activities funded through this agreement, it is more difficult to identify this time specifically with any one individual project, hence the use of Core Support to collect these direct overarching direct costs. Other costs charged to Core Support include direct system infrastructure and the development necessary to continuously maintain the level of service committed to the arctic research community under the Cooperative Agreement.

- Coordinated planning, managed emerging priorities, and supervised work on all the tasks and project activities described in this report. The portion of the Executive Director's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement is charged to the Core Support category.
- Upgraded hardware, software, and programming to expand capability for projects that require expanded server, network, and database capacity, support for NSF-sponsored meeting online registration, poster submission, and general information distribution.
- Managed the server setup, network, creation of needed technical resources, and the computing capability that directly supports the project activities. The portion of the System Administrator's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement is charged to the Core Support category. System upgrades included a number of software and hardware improvements to increase system and network efficiency and security.
- Supported staff travel to arctic research meetings and workshops that addressed topics pertaining to multiple NSF projects and activities included in the Cooperative Agreement, but which were not specific to one project.
- Concluded federal liaison work at our Washington, D.C. office in 2004 and consolidated remaining workflow and processes into the Fairbanks office.

SUMMARY

ARCUS has facilitated scientific planning for arctic research efforts for over 17 years by working with the scientific community through workshops, surveys, Internet communications, and other means to define science priorities and research initiatives. ARCUS has organized dozens of workshops and published numerous scientific planning documents that reflect the recommendations of the arctic research community on scientific priorities in various research fields. All of the activities described in this report supported community science planning processes for the NSF Arctic Sciences Division and provided information and support for the conduct of arctic research and education and, therefore, contributed to the overall excellence and advancement of arctic research and education supported by the National Science Foundation.

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Appendix: Response to Specific NSF Reporting Questions

PARTICIPANTS:

2. What other organizations have been involved as partners?

3. Have you had other collaborators or contacts?

Over the period of this agreement, ARCUS collaborated on a regular basis with the following organizations:

- Barrow Arctic Science Consortium
- CH2M HILL Polar Services
- Alaska Native Science Commission
- U.S. Arctic Research Commission
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
- North Pacific Research Board
- North Slope Borough School District
- Fairbanks North Star Borough School District

The following organizations are current ARCUS Member Institutions:

Voting Members

- Alaska North Slope Borough Department of Wildlife Management
- Arctic Centre, University of Lapland
- Arizona State University
- Bates College
- The Center for Northern Studies
- Clayton H. Riddell Faculty of Environment, Earth, and Resources, University of Manitoba
- Dartmouth College
- Desert Research Institute
- Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University
- The Foundation for Glacier and Environmental Research
- Idaho State University
- Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory of Columbia University
- Louisiana State University
- Marine Biological Laboratory
- Northern Illinois University
- The Ohio State University
- Oregon State University
- San Diego State University
- Sandia National Laboratories
- Scandinavian Seminar
- Scott Polar Research Institute

Smithsonian Institution
SRI International
Texas A&M University
University of Alaska Anchorage
University of Alaska Fairbanks
University of Alaska Statewide
University of Colorado
University of Delaware
University of Massachusetts
University of Miami
University of New Hampshire
University of Northern British Columbia
University of Washington
Vancouver Island University
Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Woods Hole Research Center

Associate Members

Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research
Association of Canadian Universities for Northern Studies (ACUNS)
Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory
Greenland National Museum and Archives
IFM-GEOMAR Research Center for Marine Geosciences
Ilisimatusarfik - University of Greenland
International Polar Foundation
McGill University
Norwegian Polar Institute
Tarfala Research Station
The University Centre in Svalbard (UNIS)
University of Tromsø
US Geological Survey

Lists of the membership of all ARCUS committees are available on the ARCUS website: www.arcus.org. The memberships of 4 major science planning committees are given here as representative of the breadth of the arctic research community involved in ARCUS activities.

ARCUS Arctic Research Support and Logistics working group, 2000–2003

Peter Schlosser, Co-chair
Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory
Columbia University

Miles McPhee
McPhee Research Company

Terry Tucker, Co-chair
Cold Regions Research & Engineering
Laboratory
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers

Craig Nicolson
Department of Natural Resources
Conservation
University of Massachusetts

Julie Brigham-Grette
Department of Geosciences
University of Massachusetts

Roger W. Smith
Geophysical Institute
University of Alaska Fairbanks

Jack Dibb
Glacier Research Group
University of New Hampshire

Matthew Sturm
Cold Regions Research & Engineering
Laboratory
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers

Jack Kruse
Department of Geosciences
University of Massachusetts

Taneil Uttal
Environmental Research Laboratory
National Oceanic & Atmospheric
Administration

ARCSS Committee, 2001–2008

Joshua Schimel, chair 2006–
Department of Ecology, Evolution, and Marine Biology
University of California Santa Barbara

Jonathan Overpeck, chair 2002–2006
Institute for the Study of Planet Earth
University of Arizona

Jack Kruse, chair, 1997–2002
Department of Geosciences
University of Massachusetts

The following have served on the ARCSS committee over this period:

F. Stuart (Terry) Chapin, III
Institute of Arctic Biology
University of Alaska Fairbanks

Lloyd D. Keigwin
Department of Geology & Geophysics
Woods Hole Oceanographic
Institution

Rudy J. Dichtl
Cooperative Institute for Research in
Environmental Sciences
University of Colorado

Amanda Lynch
Cooperative Institute for Research in
Environmental Sciences
University of Colorado, Boulder

Jennifer Francis
Institute of Marine and Coastal
Sciences
Rutgers University

Glen M. MacDonald
Departments of Geography &
Organismic Biology, Ecology &
Evolution
University of California, Los Angeles

Lawrence C. Hamilton
Department of Sociology
University of New Hampshire

Joe McFadden
Department of Ecology, Evolution, and
Behavior
University of Minnesota

O. W. (Bill) Heal
University of Edinburgh, UK

Marika Holland
Climate and Global Dynamics Division
National Center for Atmospheric
Research

Maribeth Murray
Department of Anthropology
University of Alaska Fairbanks

Craig Nicolson
Department of Natural Resources
Conservation
University of Massachusetts

Don Perovich
Cold Regions Research and
Engineering Laboratory
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers

Bruce J. Peterson
The Ecosystems Center
Marine Biological Laboratory

Michael J. Retelle
Department of Geology
Bates College

Mark Serreze
Cooperative Institute for Research in
Environmental Sciences
University of Colorado

Michael Steele
Polar Science Center - Applied Physics
Laboratory
University of Washington

Matthew Sturm
Cold Regions Research and
Engineering Laboratory
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers

Charles Vörösmarty
Water Systems Analysis Group
University of New Hampshire

John Weatherly
Cold Regions Research & Engineering
Laboratory
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers

SEARCH Science Steering Committee, 2001–2008

Jamie Morison, chair, 2001–2005
Polar Science Center - Applied Physics Lab
University of Washington, Seattle

Peter Schlosser, chair, 2005–2008
Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory
Columbia University

The following have served on this committee over this period:

Vera Alexander
School of Fisheries and Ocean Sciences
University of Alaska, Fairbanks

Roger G. Barry
Cooperative Institute for Research in
Environmental Sciences
University of Colorado

Louis A. Codispoti
Center for Environmental Science
University of Maryland

Thomas L. Delworth
Geophysical Fluid Dynamics
Laboratory
National Oceanic and Atmospheric
Administration

Bob Dickson
Centre for Environment, Fisheries and
Aquaculture Science, UK

Hajo Eicken
Geophysical Institute
University of Alaska

Mark Fahnestock
Inst. for the Study of Earth, Oceans
and Space
University of New Hampshire

Jennifer Francis
Institute of Marine and Coastal
Sciences
Rutgers University

Jacqueline M. Grebmeier
Dept. of Ecology and Evolutionary
Biology
University of Tennessee

Lawrence C. Hamilton
Department of Sociology
University of New Hampshire

Robert M. Holmes
Woods Hole Research Center

Konrad Hughen
Marine Chemistry and Geochemistry
Woods Hole Oceanographic
Institution

George L. Hunt, Jr.
School of Aquatic and Fishery Sciences
University of Washington
and Department of Ecology and
Evolutionary Biology
University of California

George Kling
Department of Biology
University of Michigan

Jack Kruse
Department of Geosciences
University of Massachusetts

Peter Rhines
School of Oceanography
University of Washington

Dennis Lettenmaier
Civil and Environmental Engineering
University of Washington

Peter P. Schweitzer
Department of Anthropology
University of Alaska

James A. Maslanik
Aerospace Engineering Sciences
University of Colorado

Mark C. Serreze
Cooperative Institute for Research in
Environmental Sciences
University of Colorado

Dave McGuire
Institute of Arctic Biology
University of Alaska

Gaius Shaver
The Ecosystems Center
Marine Biological Laboratory

Sue Moore
National Marine Mammal Laboratory
National Oceanic and Atmospheric
Administration

Michael Steele
Polar Science Center - Applied Physics
Lab
University of Washington

Jim Overland
Pacific Marine Environmental
Laboratory
National Oceanic and Atmospheric
Administration

Konrad Steffen
Cooperative Institute for Research in
Environmental Sciences
University of Colorado

Jonathan Overpeck
Institute for the Study of Planet Earth
University of Arizona

Stephen J. Vavrus
Center for Climatic Research
University of Wisconsin

Karen Pletnikoff
Community Services Department
Aleutian/Pribilof Islands Association

John Walsh
Department of Atmospheric Sciences
University of Illinois
and International Arctic Research
Center
University of Alaska

Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) Science Steering Committee, 2004–2007

George L. Hunt, Jr., chair
School of Aquatic and Fishery
Sciences
University of Washington

J. Benjamin Fitzhugh
Department of Anthropology
University of Washington

Rolf R. Gradinger
School of Fisheries and Ocean
Sciences
University of Alaska Fairbanks

Eileen Hofmann
Center for Coastal Physical
Oceanography
Old Dominion University

Henry P. Huntington
Huntington Consulting

Arthur J. Miller
Scripps Institution of Oceanography
University of California San Diego

Jeff Napp
Alaska Fisheries Science Center
National Oceanic and Atmospheric
Administration

Mary C. Pete
Kuskokwim Campus
University of Alaska Fairbanks

Karen Pletnikoff
Community Services Department
Aleutian/Pribilof Islands Association

Kenneth Rose
Coastal Fisheries Institute
Louisiana State University

Raymond Sambrotto
Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory
Columbia University

Jennifer A. Sepez
Alaska Fisheries Science Center
National Oceanic and Atmospheric
Administration

Sharon L. Smith
Rosenstiel School of Marine and
Atmospheric Sciences
University of Miami

Peter Winsor
Woods Hole Oceanographic
Institution

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Appendix: ARCUS Publications

All ARCUS publications are available as PDF downloads on the ARCUS website: www.arcus.org. The publications below are part of Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279 and are listed by date of publication.

Arctic Observation Integration: Workshops Report. 2008. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 55 pages.

Designing the Human Dimension into an Arctic Observing Network. 2007. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 2 pages.

Surface Transformations in the Arctic Environment (STATE): Implementation Plan. 2007. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 33 pages.

Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH). *Study of Environmental Arctic Change: Plans for Implementation During the International Polar Year and Beyond. Report of the SEARCH Implementation Workshop, May 23 - 25, 2005*. 2005. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 90 pages.

Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH). *Proceedings of the SEARCH Open Science Meeting, 27-30 October 2003, Seattle, Washington*. 2005. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 370 pages.

Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) Implementation Plan. 2005. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 39 pages.

Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) Science Plan. 2004. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 82 pages.

Arctic Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) for Scientific Research - White Paper. 2004. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 41 pages.

Guidelines for Improved Cooperation between Arctic Researchers and Northern Communities. 2004. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 20 pages.

ARCSS Program. *Proceedings of the Arctic System Science Program All-Hands Workshop 2002*. 2003. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 271 pages.

Arctic Research Support and Logistics: Strategies and Recommendations for System-scale Studies in a Changing Environment. 2003. Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. Fairbanks, Alaska. 95 pages.

Krupnik, I., and D. Jolly (eds.). *The Earth is Faster Now: Indigenous Observations of Arctic Environmental Change.* 2002. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 384 pages. ISBN 0-9720449-0-6.

Arctic Science Education: Recommendations from the Working Group on Arctic Science Education to the National Science Foundation. 2002. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 56 pages.

Vörösmarty, C. J., L. D. Hinzman, B. J. Peterson, D. H. Bromwich, L. C. Hamilton, J. Morison, V. E. Romanovsky, M. Sturm, and R. S. Webb. *The Hydrologic Cycle and its Role in Arctic and Global Environmental Change: A Rationale and Strategy for Synthesis Study.* 2001. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 84 pages.

Hinzman, L., and C. Vörösmarty (eds.). *NSF-ARCSS Workshop on Arctic System Hydrology: Meeting White Papers.* 2001. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 86 pages.

Taagholt, J., and J. C. Hansen. Translation by D. Lufkin. *Greenland: Security Perspectives.* 2001. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. 94 pages.

Abstracts from the Arctic Forum. 2001–2007. 7 volumes. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. Various pages.

Warnick, W., S. Behr, R. Coen, S. Mitchell, and A. York (managing eds.). *Witness the Arctic.* 2001–2007. 8 issues. Fairbanks, Alaska: Arctic Research Consortium of the United States. Various pages.

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<u>Form 1030 Category</u>		7 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actual	Year 2 Actual	Year 3 Actual	Year 4 Actual	Year 5 Actual	Year 6 Actual	Year 7 Actual	Expenditures Total Project	Funds Remaining (Shortfall)
Salaries											
President	A1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Executive director	A2	453,216	67,420	57,768	63,491	66,154	75,660	74,168	85,611	490,271	(37,055)
Other professionals	B2	2,162,792	257,366	242,803	364,762	363,887	416,368	366,408	328,025	2,339,619	(176,827)
Student	B3	119,191	8,411	11,243	19,755	13,431	13,909	17,054	45,134	128,935	(9,744)
Clerical	B5	383,767	39,702	28,656	50,523	50,640	55,010	84,112	106,501	415,144	(31,377)
Total salaries		3,118,967	372,898	340,470	498,530	494,112	560,947	541,741	565,271	3,373,969	(255,002)
Fringe Benefits											
Total salaries and fringe benefits	C	1,185,208	122,621	112,614	167,812	169,635	229,517	220,276	236,690	1,259,166	(73,958)
		4,304,175	495,519	453,084	666,342	663,747	790,464	762,017	801,961	4,633,134	(328,959)
Permanent Equipment											
	D	21,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	20,800	20,800	200
Travel (domestic)											
	E1	522,902	60,039	58,308	94,814	52,138	68,283	95,262	146,109	574,953	(52,051)
Travel (foreign)											
	E2	16,225	-	-	-	-	3,040	8,506	5,872	17,418	(1,193)
Participant Support Costs											
Stipends	F1	29,107	14,800	8,588	(4,938)	1,450	2,800	4,300	2,000	29,000	107
Travel	F2	597,767	54,779	39,726	101,431	50,340	102,524	90,641	156,126	595,567	2,200
Subsistence	F3	688,296	72,354	33,307	115,715	58,153	116,866	70,224	219,144	685,764	2,532
Total participant costs		1,315,170	141,933	81,620	212,208	109,944	222,190	165,165	377,270	1,310,331	4,839
Other Direct Costs											
Materials and supplies	G1	403,338	80,640	55,259	66,565	37,644	49,005	58,692	39,888	387,693	15,645
Publication cost/ docum/dissem	G2	531,411	63,719	94,753	93,639	69,224	51,408	50,146	87,909	510,799	20,612
Consultant services	G3	705,684	111,585	142,908	142,643	126,100	56,527	56,498	42,050	678,312	27,372
Computer services	G4	147,564	1,815	11,436	1,018	22,400	37,559	24,691	42,921	141,840	5,724
Subcontracts	G5	566,507	-	30,627	121,698	69,902	170,679	102,003	49,625	544,533	21,974
Other	G6	1,056,383	107,196	38,759	249,716	59,555	135,817	151,010	273,356	1,015,409	40,974
Total other direct costs		3,410,887	364,955	373,741	675,279	384,824	500,996	443,039	535,749	3,278,585	132,302
Total direct costs	H	9,590,360	1,062,446	966,753	1,648,644	1,210,653	1,584,972	1,473,991	1,887,762	9,835,221	(244,861)
Indirect											
	I	3,463,181	411,569	331,453	551,918	411,100	502,710	470,047	539,523	3,218,320	244,861
TOTAL	J	13,053,541	1,474,015	1,298,206	2,200,562	1,621,753	2,087,682	1,944,038	2,427,285	13,053,541	(0)

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	7 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actual	Year 2 Actual	Year 3 Actual	Year 4 Actual	Year 5 Actual	Year 6 Actual	Year 7 Actual	Expenditures Total Project	Cumulative Funds Remaining (Shortfall)
1 ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING										
1.1 Arctic Logistics	134,312	19,068	23,874	53,130	1,122	311	290	43	97,837	36,475
1.2 ALIAS Website	603,700	96,470	128,702	140,337	86,171	64,260	-	-	515,940	87,760
1.3 GIS Planning	80,700	35,460	100	14,240	4,312	2,393	4,625	20,634	81,763	(1,063)
1.4a SEARCH Planning	1,051,318	-	6,297	307,033	20,028	307,940	147,267	307,263	1,095,829	(44,511)
1.4b SEARCH OSM Student Support	28,776	-	-	28,776	-	-	-	-	28,776	(0)
1.5 Bering Sea Planning	229,406	-	32,877	54,615	13,863	41,502	57,128	31,909	231,894	(2,488)
1.6 Workshop TBD	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1.7 SEARCH Brochure	5,735	5,742	-	-	-	-	-	-	5,742	(7)
1.8 Arctic Data Survey	11,635	-	-	1,335	6,150	-	-	5,325	12,811	(1,176)
SubTotal Direct Costs	2,145,582	156,739	191,850	599,466	131,646	416,406	209,310	365,174	2,070,592	74,990
Indirect Costs	828,616	62,769	67,492	218,143	47,240	125,210	66,235	102,936	690,025	138,591
TOTAL	2,974,198	219,508	259,342	817,609	178,886	541,616	275,545	468,110	2,760,617	213,581
2 NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION										
2.1 Arctic Section Science Materials	36,042	7,040	2,805	1,084	1,333	3,031	188	95	15,576	20,466
2.2 ARCSS Program Coordination										
2.2.1 ARCSS Coordination	2,090,247	30,274	117,883	239,688	311,685	361,138	290,521	658,920	2,010,109	80,138
2.2.2 ARCSS All-Hands Workshop	318,564	259,826	42,448	3,226	-	-	-	-	305,500	13,064
2.2.3 HARC SMO	185,753	44,449	29,400	91,495	-	-	-	-	165,344	20,409
2.2.4 Arctic Hydrology Report	18,275	18,276	-	-	-	-	-	-	18,276	(1)
SubTotal 2.2 Direct Costs	2,612,839	352,825	189,731	334,409	311,685	361,138	290,521	658,920	2,499,230	113,610
2.3 ASSP Program Coordination										
2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Planning	182,135	6,466	7,856	70,518	4,774	2,209	7,956	-	99,780	82,355
2.3.2 Greenland Book	12,263	12,263	-	-	-	-	-	-	12,263	0
2.3.3 Arctic Social Sciences Volume	35,886	15,933	23,172	955	-	-	-	-	40,060	(4,174)
2.3.4 Bering Sea Community Planning	92,215	-	-	15,401	6,438	31,680	277	9,578	63,373	28,842
SubTotal 2.3 Direct Costs	322,499	34,662	31,028	86,875	11,212	33,889	8,233	9,578	215,476	107,023
2.4 ANS Program Coordination										
2.4.1 ANS materials	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sub-Total Direct Costs	2,971,380	394,526	223,564	422,368	324,230	398,057	298,944	668,593	2,730,281	241,099
Indirect Costs	871,104	147,151	67,856	107,616	92,297	104,405	69,970	183,227	772,521	98,583
TOTAL	3,842,484	541,676	291,420	529,985	416,527	502,462	368,913	851,820	3,502,803	339,682
3 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION										
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities	41,570	10,847	7,999	(0)	-	-	3,732	10,545	33,122	8,448
3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers Program	164,998	37,130	21,671	24,064	23,116	22,505	21,375	34,322	184,183	(19,185)
3.3 Arctic Science Education Report	42,275	7,691	14,559	-	-	-	-	-	22,250	20,025
3.4 ARCTIC ALIVE!	27,996	-	-	27,996	-	-	-	-	27,996	(0)
3.5 TREC	215,489	-	-	36,290	58,904	97,031	130,631	-	322,855	(107,366)
SubTotal Direct Costs	492,328	55,668	44,229	88,350	82,020	119,536	155,737	44,866	590,406	(98,078)
Indirect Costs	195,564	22,244	15,850	32,397	29,453	42,500	53,839	12,548	208,833	(13,268)
TOTAL	687,892	77,912	60,079	120,748	111,473	162,036	209,577	57,414	799,239	(111,347)
4 INFORMATION AND OUTREACH										
4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletter	431,659	53,942	84,977	46,540	77,513	39,280	93,663	48,797	444,712	(13,052)
4.2 Web Site/Internet Resources	683,272	68,739	54,937	89,308	124,830	123,734	135,380	135,929	732,857	(49,585)
4.3 Arctic Info Listserv	122,374	12,508	12,286	20,013	21,919	28,819	33,020	24,876	153,442	(31,068)
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers	74,195	8,087	17,428	9,319	8,671	12,178	3,045	4,226	62,955	11,240
4.5 Internet Graphics Archive	129,659	-	13,734	424	16,730	29,061	35,329	17,130	112,408	17,251
4.6 Community Outreach	660,999	46,872	53,801	50,479	88,430	133,836	189,399	203,339	766,155	(105,156)
4.7 Publication: The Arctic	48,574	619	55	-	83	-	1,324	-	2,081	46,493
4.8 Endangered Species Bulletin	2,713	2,150	468	-	-	-	-	-	2,618	95
SubTotal Direct Costs	2,153,445	192,917	237,685	216,084	338,176	366,908	491,161	434,297	2,277,228	(123,783)
Indirect Costs	844,260	76,130	84,622	78,132	120,960	130,049	172,005	131,477	793,376	50,884
TOTAL	2,997,705	269,047	322,307	294,216	459,136	496,957	663,166	565,774	3,070,603	(72,898)
5 CORE SUPPORT										
Core Support										
SubTotal Direct Costs	1,827,625	262,598	269,425	322,376	334,580	284,067	318,839	374,832	2,166,717	(339,093)
Indirect Costs	723,636	103,275	95,633	115,629	121,150	100,544	107,998	109,334	753,563	(29,927)
TOTAL	2,551,261	365,873	365,058	438,005	455,729	384,611	426,837	484,166	2,920,280	(369,019)
TOTAL COSTS	13,053,541	1,474,015	1,298,206	2,200,562	1,621,753	2,087,682	1,944,038	2,427,285	13,053,541	(0)

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	7 Year Cumulative Budget	Year 1 Actual	Year 2 Actual	Year 3 Actual	Year 4 Actual	Year 5 Actual	Year 6 Actual	Year 7 Actual	Cumulative Total Project Expenses	Cumulative Funds Remaining (Shortfall)
1 Arctic Community Science Planning										
1.1 ARCTIC LOGISTICS										
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	68,575	9,479	20,457	31,822	1,037	311	290	43	63,439	5,136
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	11,119	4,127	2,077	1,761	-	-	-	-	7,965	3,154
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	9,102	2,634	604	-	-	-	-	-	3,238	5,864
Other Direct Costs	45,516	2,828	736	19,547	85	-	-	-	23,196	22,320
Total direct costs	134,312	19,068	23,874	53,130	1,122	311	290	43	97,837	36,475
Indirect Costs	56,451	7,582	8,437	19,043	392	107	91	13	35,667	20,784
Total direct and indirect costs	190,763	26,650	32,311	72,173	1,514	418	381	56	133,504	57,259
1.2 ALIAS WEBSITE										
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	395,481	60,048	80,628	101,646	66,377	50,742	-	-	359,441	36,040
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	66,172	14,437	14,164	11,272	10,055	373	-	-	50,301	15,872
Travel (foreign)	5,747	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5,747
Participant Support Costs	1,254	-	1,254	-	-	1,449	-	-	2,702	(1,448)
Other Direct Costs	135,046	21,985	32,656	27,419	9,739	11,697	-	-	103,496	31,550
Total direct costs	603,700	96,470	128,702	140,337	86,171	64,260	-	-	515,940	87,760
Indirect Costs	244,057	37,900	45,517	49,653	31,111	22,579	-	-	186,760	57,297
Total direct and indirect costs	847,757	134,370	174,219	189,990	117,282	86,840	-	-	702,700	145,056
1.3 GIS PLANNING										
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	49,942	20,920	-	4,936	4,265	1,022	4,612	19,146	54,900	(4,958)
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	5,561	2,294	-	-	-	1,081	13	-	3,388	2,173
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	9,688	8,050	-	1,638	-	-	-	-	9,688	(0)
Other Direct Costs	15,509	4,196	100	7,666	47	290	-	1,488	13,788	1,721
Total direct costs	80,700	35,460	100	14,240	4,312	2,393	4,625	20,634	81,763	(1,063)
Indirect Costs	32,785	14,902	34	5,323	1,595	826	1,458	5,794	29,933	2,853
Total direct and indirect costs	113,485	50,362	134	19,563	5,907	3,219	6,083	26,428	111,696	1,789
1.4a SEARCH PLANNING										
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	385,371	-	729	79,131	9,948	97,390	41,693	92,518	321,409	63,962
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic and foreign)	76,486	-	3,312	16,241	552	21,857	15,693	20,846	78,502	(2,016)
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	8,506	6,003	14,509	(14,509)
Participant Support Costs	220,418	-	225	44,180	980	71,944	36,845	88,964	243,138	(22,720)
Other Direct Costs	369,043	-	2,031	167,481	8,548	116,749	44,530	98,932	438,271	(69,228)
Total direct costs	1,051,318	-	6,297	307,033	20,028	307,940	147,267	307,263	1,095,830	(44,512)
Indirect Costs	384,127	-	2,171	113,207	7,053	87,285	44,225	86,103	340,044	44,083
Total direct and indirect costs	1,435,445	-	8,468	420,240	27,081	395,225	191,493	393,366	1,435,873	(428)
1.4b SEARCH OSM Student Support										
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic and foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	27,945	-	-	27,945	-	-	-	-	27,945	(0)
Other Direct Costs	831	-	-	831	-	-	-	-	831	0
Total direct costs	28,776	-	-	28,776	-	-	-	-	28,776	(0)
Indirect Costs	12,374	-	-	10,757	-	-	-	-	10,757	1,617
Total direct and indirect costs	41,150	-	-	39,533	-	-	-	-	39,533	1,617
1.5 BERING SEA PLANNING										
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	77,032	-	3,919	23,081	16,665	15,408	20,921	14,655	94,649	(17,617)
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	10,266	-	8,205	(825)	-	2,885	3,576	2,960	16,801	(6,535)
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	88,231	-	19,749	(3,508)	-	19,056	28,569	11,353	75,219	13,012
Other Direct Costs	53,877	-	1,004	35,867	(2,802)	4,153	4,062	2,941	45,224	8,653
Total direct costs	229,406	-	32,877	54,615	13,863	41,502	57,128	31,909	231,894	(2,488)
Indirect Costs	91,915	-	11,333	19,662	4,967	14,412	20,461	9,570	80,404	11,511
Total direct and indirect costs	321,321	-	44,210	74,277	18,830	55,915	77,589	41,478	312,298	9,023
1.6 WKSP TBD										
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1.7 SEARCH BROCHURE										

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	1,083	1,090	-	-	-	-	-	-	1,090	(7)
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	4,652	4,652	-	-	-	-	-	-	4,652	-
Total direct costs	5,735	5,742	-	-	-	-	-	-	5,742	(7)
Indirect Costs	2,419	2,384	-	-	-	-	-	-	2,384	35
Total direct and indirect costs	8,154	8,126	-	-	-	-	-	-	8,126	28

1.8 ARCTIC DATA SURVEY

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	985	-	-	235	-	-	-	2,377	2,612	(1,627)
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	2,400	-	-	-	-	-	-	2,933	2,933	(533)
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	8,250	-	-	1,100	6,150	-	-	16	7,266	984
Total direct costs	11,635	-	-	1,335	6,150	-	-	5,325	12,811	(1,176)
Indirect Costs	4,488	-	-	499	2,122	-	-	1,457	4,077	411
Total direct and indirect costs	16,123	-	-	1,834	8,272	-	-	6,782	16,888	(765)

1.9 SEARCH SMO

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

2 NSF Arctic Sciences Section Coordination**2.1 ARCTIC SECTION SCIENCE MATERIALS**

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	17,419	6,799	1,597	210	-	3,031	188	95	11,919	5,500
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	18,623	241	1,208	874	1,333	-	-	-	3,656	14,967
Total direct costs	36,042	7,040	2,805	1,084	1,333	3,031	188	95	15,575	20,467
Indirect Costs	14,877	2,585	967	378	460	1,116	66	26	5,597	9,280
Total direct and indirect costs	50,919	9,625	3,772	1,462	1,793	4,147	255	121	21,172	29,747

2.2 ARCSS PROGRAM COORDINATION**2.2.1 ARCSS COORDINATION**

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	420,668	9,127	23,970	41,862	91,541	78,366	108,015	171,460	524,341	(103,673)
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	113,357	4,244	12,718	24,364	18,847	8,600	30,083	71,883	170,738	(57,381)
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	467,582	10,677	29,379	56,955	72,074	65,938	11,734	222,626	469,384	(1,802)
Other Direct Costs	1,088,640	6,226	51,816	116,507	129,223	208,234	140,689	192,952	845,646	242,994
Total direct costs	2,090,247	30,274	117,883	239,688	311,685	361,138	290,521	658,920	2,010,109	80,138
Indirect Costs	547,491	11,220	30,333	59,306	87,461	91,014	67,071	180,306	526,711	20,780
Total direct and indirect costs	2,637,738	41,494	148,216	298,994	399,146	452,152	357,592	839,226	2,536,821	100,917

2.2.1.1 ARCSS SMO

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

2.2.2 ARCSS ALL-HANDS WORKSHOP

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	69,029	46,331	23,683	2,059	-	-	-	-	72,073	(3,044)
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	14,943	17,182	(294)	-	-	-	-	-	16,887	(1,944)
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	86,986	89,230	1,284	-	-	-	-	-	90,513	(3,527)
Other Direct Costs	147,606	107,083	17,775	1,167	-	-	-	-	126,025	21,581
Total direct costs	318,564	259,826	42,448	3,226	-	-	-	-	305,498	13,066
Indirect Costs	134,401	95,062	15,015	1,112	-	-	-	-	111,189	23,212
Total direct and indirect costs	452,965	354,888	57,463	4,338	-	-	-	-	416,687	36,278

2.2.3 HARC SMO

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	49,025	20,151	6,780	20,236	-	-	-	-	47,167	1,859
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	11,985	1,249	953	4,441	-	-	-	-	6,643	5,342
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	29,749	1,686	3,891	24,269	-	-	-	-	29,846	(97)
Other Direct Costs	94,994	21,363	17,776	42,549	-	-	-	-	81,687	13,307

Total direct costs	185,753	44,449	29,400	91,495	-	-	-	-	165,343	20,410
Indirect Costs	78,111	17,120	10,416	33,249	243	-	-	-	61,028	17,083
Total direct and indirect costs	263,864	61,569	39,816	124,744	243	-	-	-	226,371	37,494

2.2.4 ARCTIC HYDROLOGY REPORT

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	16,279	16,279	-	-	-	-	-	-	16,279	(0)
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	1,996	1,997	-	-	-	-	-	-	1,997	(1)
Total direct costs	18,275	18,276	-	-	-	-	-	-	18,276	(1)
Indirect Costs	7,709	7,477	-	-	-	-	-	-	7,477	232
Total direct and indirect costs	25,984	25,753	-	-	-	-	-	-	25,753	231

2.3 ASSP PROGRAM COORDINATION**2.3.1 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES WORKSHOP**

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	35,433	6,166	4,001	6,600	4,338	-	-	-	21,105	14,328
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	6,308	46	3,241	3,021	-	-	-	-	6,308	(0)
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	5,560	-	-	4,435	362	2,209	6,003	-	13,010	(7,450)
Other Direct Costs	134,834	254	614	56,462	74	-	1,953	-	59,358	75,476
Total direct costs	182,135	6,466	7,856	70,518	4,774	2,209	7,956	-	99,781	82,354
Indirect Costs	33,262	2,716	2,711	7,485	1,782	810	2,742	-	18,246	15,015
Total direct and indirect costs	215,397	9,182	10,567	78,003	6,556	3,019	10,698	-	118,026	97,371

2.3.2 GREENLAND BOOK

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	1,326	1,326	-	-	-	-	-	-	1,326	0
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	10,937	10,937	-	-	-	-	-	-	10,937	-
Total direct costs	12,263	12,263	-	-	-	-	-	-	12,263	0
Indirect Costs	5,172	5,172	-	-	-	-	-	-	5,172	(0)
Total direct and indirect costs	17,435	17,435	-	-	-	-	-	-	17,435	(0)

2.3.3 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES VOLUME

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	7,202	2,733	5,371	107	-	-	-	-	8,211	(1,009)
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	1,556	-	1,556	-	-	-	-	-	1,556	0
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	13,380	-	2,380	458	-	-	-	-	2,838	10,542
Other Direct Costs	13,748	13,200	13,865	390	-	-	-	-	27,455	(13,707)
Total direct costs	35,886	15,933	23,172	955	-	-	-	-	40,060	(4,174)
Indirect Costs	15,067	5,798	8,414	329	-	-	-	-	14,541	526
Total direct and indirect costs	50,953	21,731	31,586	1,284	-	-	-	-	54,601	(3,648)

2.3.4 BERING SEA COMMUNITY PLANNING

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	36,033	-	-	2,997	2,025	8,466	277	9,423	23,187	12,846
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	3,540	-	-	537	(10)	1,126	-	-	1,653	1,887
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	19,136	-	-	11,796	217	16,860	-	-	28,873	(9,737)
Other Direct Costs	33,506	-	-	71	4,206	5,228	-	155	9,660	23,846
Total direct costs	92,215	-	-	15,401	6,438	31,680	277	9,578	63,372	28,843
Indirect Costs	35,014	-	-	5,757	2,351	11,466	90	2,895	22,559	12,455
Total direct and indirect costs	127,229	-	-	21,158	8,789	43,145	367	12,473	85,931	41,298

2.4 ANS PROGRAM COORDINATION**2.4.1 ANS MATERIALS**

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

3 Arctic Science Education**3.1 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION ACTIVITIES**

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	24,558	8,181	7,290	(0)	-	-	-	7,771	23,243	1,315
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	739	739	-	-	-	-	2,071	-	2,810	(2,071)
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	(131)	(131)	131
Participant Support Costs	6,547	-	548	-	-	-	1,626	1,931	4,105	2,442
Other Direct Costs	9,726	1,927	161	-	-	-	35	972	3,095	6,631
Total direct costs	41,570	10,847	7,999	(0)	-	-	3,732	10,545	33,122	8,448
Indirect Costs	16,744	4,325	2,853	27	-	-	1,171	2,940	11,317	5,427
Total direct and indirect costs	58,314	15,172	10,852	27	-	-	4,902	13,485	44,439	13,875

3.2 ARCTIC VISITING SPEAKERS PROGRAM

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	51,653	9,599	8,353	8,251	10,446	10,470	7,607	16,122	70,848	(19,195)
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OPP-0101279
 Task Summary
 FINAL REPORT

Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	112,537	27,301	13,195	15,612	12,534	12,026	13,680	14,286	108,635	3,902
Other Direct Costs	808	230	123	201	136	9	89	3,913	4,700	(3,892)
Total direct costs	164,998	37,130	21,671	24,064	23,116	22,505	21,375	34,322	184,183	(19,185)
Indirect Costs	65,945	14,772	7,740	8,690	8,167	8,042	7,370	9,608	64,390	1,555
Total direct and indirect costs	230,943	51,902	29,411	32,754	31,283	30,547	28,744	43,930	248,573	(17,630)

3.3 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION REPORT

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	10,633	7,691	2,178	-	-	-	-	-	9,869	764
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	458	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	458
Other Direct Costs	31,184	-	12,381	-	-	-	-	-	12,381	18,803
Total direct costs	42,275	7,691	14,559	-	-	-	-	-	22,250	20,025
Indirect Costs	17,756	3,147	5,257	-	-	-	-	-	8,404	9,351
Total direct and indirect costs	60,031	10,838	19,816	-	-	-	-	-	30,654	29,376

3.4 ARCTIC ALIVE

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	18,053	-	-	18,053	-	-	-	-	18,053	0
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	4,774	-	-	4,774	-	-	-	-	4,774	(0)
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	3,762	-	-	3,762	-	-	-	-	3,762	0
Other Direct Costs	1,407	-	-	1,407	-	-	-	-	1,407	(0)
Total direct costs	27,996	-	-	27,996	-	-	-	-	27,996	(0)
Indirect Costs	11,627	-	-	10,114	-	-	-	-	10,114	1,513
Total direct and indirect costs	39,623	-	-	38,110	-	-	-	-	38,110	1,513

3.5 TREC

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	124,622	-	-	19,418	45,098	65,175	79,412	-	209,104	(84,482)
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	1,989	-	-	-	-	943	4,575	-	5,518	(3,529)
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	23,550	-	-	-	-	9,052	14,364	-	23,417	133
Other Direct Costs	65,328	-	-	16,872	13,806	21,860	32,280	-	84,818	(19,490)
Total direct costs	215,489	-	-	36,290	58,904	97,031	130,631	-	322,855	(107,367)
Indirect Costs	83,492	-	-	13,565	21,286	34,459	45,299	-	114,610	(31,118)
Total direct and indirect costs	298,981	-	-	49,855	80,190	131,491	175,930	-	437,465	(138,485)

4 Information and Outreach**4.1 WITNESS THE ARCTIC NEWSLETTERS**

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	234,925	22,734	34,201	21,812	45,795	34,409	60,318	9,348	228,616	6,310
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	794	794	-	-	-	-	-	-	794	(0)
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	195,940	30,414	50,776	24,728	31,718	4,871	33,345	39,449	215,302	(19,362)
Total direct costs	431,659	53,942	84,977	46,540	77,513	39,280	93,663	48,797	444,713	(13,053)
Indirect Costs	172,629	20,799	30,120	17,369	27,264	14,248	32,347	15,228	157,375	15,254
Total direct and indirect costs	604,288	74,741	115,097	63,909	104,777	53,528	126,009	64,025	602,088	2,201

4.2 INTERNET RESOURCES

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	611,554	52,897	47,674	74,125	110,240	116,446	124,731	132,411	658,525	(46,971)
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	21,889	1,740	1,330	7,029	5,791	7,113	10,171	3,162	36,335	(14,446)
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	49,829	14,102	5,933	8,154	8,799	175	478	356	37,997	11,832
Total direct costs	683,272	68,739	54,937	89,308	124,830	123,734	135,380	135,929	732,855	(49,583)
Indirect Costs	267,841	27,186	19,406	32,370	44,669	44,057	46,097	39,695	253,481	14,360
Total direct and indirect costs	951,113	95,925	74,343	121,679	169,500	167,790	181,477	175,625	986,336	(35,223)

4.3 ARCTIC INFO LISTSERVER

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	117,781	12,430	10,446	20,013	19,244	28,819	33,020	24,876	148,847	(31,066)
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	4,593	78	1,840	-	2,675	-	-	-	4,593	-
Total direct costs	122,374	12,508	12,286	20,013	21,919	28,819	33,020	24,876	153,440	(31,066)
Indirect Costs	48,216	4,915	4,377	7,214	7,900	10,312	11,279	7,297	53,294	(5,078)
Total direct and indirect costs	170,590	17,423	16,663	27,227	29,819	39,130	44,299	32,174	206,734	(36,143)

4.4 DIRECTORY OF ARCTIC RESEARCHERS

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	41,524	7,899	5,228	7,769	5,771	3,378	2,445	3,526	36,018	5,506
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	32,671	188	12,200	1,550	2,900	8,800	600	700	26,938	5,733
Total direct costs	74,195	8,087	17,428	9,319	8,671	12,178	3,045	4,226	62,956	11,239
Indirect Costs	29,744	3,236	6,292	3,324	3,385	4,250	1,037	1,212	22,735	7,009
Total direct and indirect costs	103,939	11,323	23,720	12,643	12,056	16,428	4,083	5,438	85,691	18,249

4.5 INTERNET GRAPHICS ARCHIVE

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	114,020	-	6,966	399	14,562	29,041	32,517	13,358	96,842	17,178
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	2,500	-	-	-	-	-	2,151	3,268	5,419	(2,919)
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	13,139	-	6,768	25	2,168	20	662	504	10,147	2,992
Total direct costs	129,659	-	13,734	424	16,730	29,061	35,329	17,130	112,408	17,251
Indirect Costs	49,910	-	4,847	147	5,772	10,375	11,970	5,033	38,144	11,767
Total direct and indirect costs	179,569	-	18,581	571	22,502	39,436	47,299	22,163	150,552	29,017

4.6 ARCTIC COMMUNITY OUTREACH

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	153,824	13,743	13,784	10,341	30,283	47,984	57,529	64,874	238,539	(84,715)
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	67,511	1,417	-	4,760	4,584	16,414	12,843	29,949	69,966	(2,455)
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	189,285	2,356	9,112	24,665	23,776	23,544	52,343	36,409	172,206	17,079
Other Direct Costs	250,379	29,356	30,905	10,713	29,787	45,894	66,683	72,106	285,445	(35,066)
Total direct costs	660,999	46,872	53,801	50,479	88,430	133,836	189,399	203,339	766,155	(105,156)
Indirect Costs	256,280	18,972	19,391	17,708	31,941	46,808	68,789	63,012	266,621	(10,341)
Total direct and indirect costs	917,279	65,844	73,192	68,187	120,371	180,645	258,187	266,350	1,032,776	(115,497)

4.7 PUBLICATION: THE ARCTIC

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	26,299	344	55	-	83	-	1,302	-	1,784	24,515
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	22,275	275	-	-	-	-	22	-	297	21,978
Total direct costs	48,574	619	55	-	83	-	1,324	-	2,081	46,493
Indirect Costs	18,497	239	20	-	29	-	487	-	775	17,722
Total direct and indirect costs	67,071	858	75	-	112	-	1,812	-	2,857	64,215

4.8 ENDANGERED SPECIES BULLETIN

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	2,713	2,150	468	-	-	-	-	-	2,617	96
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	2,713	2,150	468	-	-	-	-	-	2,617	96
Indirect Costs	1,143	782	170	-	-	-	-	-	952	191
Total direct and indirect costs	3,856	2,932	638	-	-	-	-	-	3,569	287

5 Core Support

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	1,141,134	157,403	145,307	171,239	186,028	200,007	187,140	219,958	1,267,082	(125,949)
Permanent Equipment	21,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	20,800	20,800	200
Travel (domestic)	99,013	11,770	11,046	17,437	12,321	7,891	14,088	11,108	85,661	13,352
Travel (foreign)	10,478	-	-	-	-	3,040	-	-	3,040	7,439
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	112	-	1,701	1,812	(1,812)
Other Direct Costs	556,000	93,425	113,072	133,700	136,231	73,017	117,612	121,265	788,321	(232,321)
Total direct costs	1,827,625	262,598	269,425	322,376	334,580	284,067	318,839	374,832	2,166,717	(339,094)
Indirect Costs	723,636	103,275	95,633	115,629	121,150	100,544	107,998	109,334	753,563	(29,927)
Total direct and indirect costs	2,551,261	365,873	365,058	438,005	455,729	384,611	426,837	484,166	2,920,280	(369,020)

TOTAL PROGRAMS

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	4,304,176	495,519	453,084	666,342	663,747	790,464	762,017	801,961	4,633,135	(328,959)
Permanent Equipment	21,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	20,800	20,800	200
Travel (domestic)	522,902	60,039	58,308	94,814	52,138	68,283	95,262	146,109	574,953	(52,051)
Travel (foreign)	16,225	-	-	-	-	3,040	8,506	5,872	17,418	(1,194)
Participant Support Costs	1,315,170	141,933	81,620	212,208	109,944	222,190	165,165	377,270	1,310,330	4,840
Other Direct Costs	3,410,887	364,955	373,741	675,280	384,824	500,995	443,040	535,749	3,278,585	132,302
Total direct costs	9,590,360	1,062,446	966,753	1,648,644	1,210,653	1,584,972	1,473,991	1,887,762	9,835,221	(244,861)
Indirect Costs	3,463,181	411,569	331,453	551,918	411,100	502,710	470,047	539,523	3,218,320	244,861
Total direct and indirect costs	13,053,541	1,474,015	1,298,206	2,200,562	1,621,753	2,087,682	1,944,038	2,427,285	13,053,541	(0)